

D5.3. Relationship between soil biodiversity, crop yield and quality and delivery of ecosystem services

SoildiverAgro

Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external inputs reduction and crop performance increase

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1 Prokaryotic diversity

1.1 Introduction

Prokaryotes, including bacteria and archaea, play a fundamental role in agricultural soils by driving critical ecosystem processes such as nutrient cycling, organic matter decomposition, and soil structure maintenance (Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2020). These microorganisms are essential for soil fertility and plant health, as they enhance nutrient availability and promote plant growth through various symbiotic interactions (Babin et al., 2019; Berendsen et al., 2012; Wagg et al., 2014). Consequently, preserving a high diversity of prokaryotes in agricultural soils is crucial.

Agricultural practices significantly impact the diversity and functionality of soil prokaryotes (Babin et al., 2019; Levine et al., 2011; Tilman et al., 2002). Interventions such as tillage, crop rotation, and the application of fertilizers and pesticides can modify the physical and chemical properties of the soil, thereby influencing microbial communities (Cozim-Melges et al., 2024).

This section of the report explores the relationships between soil prokaryotic biodiversity, crop yield, and quality, and ecosystem service delivery across the WP5 case studies conducted across six European regions. Ecosystem services analyzed include greenhouse gas emissions, soil carbon content, nutrient levels, bulk density, pH, and other key soil chemical and physical parameters. Findings are based on results from the final monitoring period for each case study. Data are presented separately for each case study to provide detailed insights.

1.2 Material and Methods

1.2.1 DNA extractions, qPCR and sequencing

The DNA extraction, amplicon sequencing and qPCR of functional genes was conducted according to protocol described in the Handbook (Lassen and Brandt, 2020) and described in the previously published D5.2 report.

1.2.2 Bioinformatics

Bioinformatics for the bacterial 16s rRNA gene sequence data was conducted using the DADA2 pipeline (Callahan et al., 2016) as described in the previously published D5.2 report.

1.2.3 Statistics

All analyses were conducted in R version 4.3.3 (R Core Team 2018) and R studio version 12.1.402. All figures were constructed using “microeco” (Liu et al., 2021), ‘phyloseq’ (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013), “vegan” and ‘ggplot2’ (Wickham, 2016) R packages.

Beta-diversity was investigated with non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) with stable solution from random starts, axis scaling and species scores with function metaMDS in ‘vegan’ package 2.5-5 (vegan, 2012) by using Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index. Environmental factors and soil physiochemical parameters (data available in Annexes) were used in the NMDS to investigate their effects on the variation in prokaryotic ASV composition using the *envfit* function of the vegan package. Only the environmental factors or soil physiochemical parameters deemed to be significantly ($p < 0.05$) associated with the prokaryotic community composition were included in the NMDS plot. Correlations between abundances of taxa, functional genes and soil physiochemical and environmental properties were investigated using Spearman’s rank test.

1.3 Results and Discussion

1.3.1 Relationship between soil ecosystem services and prokaryotic β -diversity

Case Studies 1 and 2 – Mediterranean South region

As reported in D5.2, prokaryotic β -diversity in Case Study 1 was significantly impacted by the applied treatment. Further analysis revealed that the shift in community composition was significantly associated with fruit/tuber weight (FWEIG), field moisture (Fma), and CaCO_3 content (Figure 1.1). Specifically, FWEIG and Fma were associated with the treatment-induced shift in community composition. In Case Study 2, no significant treatment effect was observed. However, several environmental parameters were significantly correlated with the community composition, including CaCO_3 content, pH (KCl), cation exchange capacity (CEC), and sum of bases (Bs). We also explored potential associations between the 40 most abundant genera and environmental properties but did not find any significant correlations (Figures A1.1 and A1.2).

Figure 1.1. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the prokaryotic Amplicon sequence variant (ASV) composition of case studies 1 and 2 (CS1 and CS2, respectively) implemented in the Mediterranean South pedoclimatic region. Vectors (red arrows) represent environmental variables that were significantly associated with the observed variations in prokaryotic community compositions ($p < 0.05$). The length of the arrows represents the strength of the correlation between the prokaryotic community composition and environmental properties. Abbreviations for CS1 are: Ctrl, control with conventional chemical fertilization; fert50, reduced chemical fertilization by 50%; red50Nuve, reduced chemical fertilization by 50% plus “Nuve” (fungi + bacteria) inoculant; red50Bacto, with “Bactoneco” (PGPB) inoculant. Abbreviations for CS2 are: Ctrl, control with standard organic fertilization; org70, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% plus bacterial inoculant; org70BioBa, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% plus bacterial and fungal inoculants.

Case Studies 3, 4 and 5 – Lusitanian region

The prokaryotic community composition in Case Studies 4 and 5 was significantly impacted by the respective treatments, as reported in D5.2. In Case Study 4, the community composition was significantly associated with several parameters, including bioavailable metals (Znba, Mnba), field moisture content (Fma), NO_3 , MDS, exchangeable elements (Caex, Mgex, Naex), and total organic carbon (TOC) (Figure 1.2). Most of these parameters were significantly positively correlated with specific genera, especially *Candidatus Udeabacter* and *Gaiella*, while negatively correlated with *Nitrolancea* and *Paenibacillus* (Figure A1.4). In Case Study 5, the treatment-induced shift in community composition was associated with changes in pH, Fma, exchangeable Ca (Caex), and sum of bases (Bs). Surprisingly, no associations were observed between these parameters and the most abundant genera (Figure A1.5). In Case Study 3, no significant treatment effect on prokaryotic community composition was observed. However, several environmental parameters were significantly linked with the community composition, including pH, available phosphorus (Pav), aggregate size distribution (Agsd_c, Agsd_d, Agsd_e), bulk density (BD), organic matter (OM), MDS, Fma, and CEC. The genus *Pseudolabrys*, was significantly positively associated with pH and negatively associated with Pav (Figure A1.3).

Figure 1.2. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the prokaryotic Amplicon sequence variant (ASV) composition of case studies 3, 4 and 5 (CS3, CS4 and CS5, respectively) implemented in the Lusitanian pedoclimatic region. Vectors (red arrows) represent environmental variables that were significantly associated with the observed variations in prokaryotic community compositions ($p < 0.05$). The length of the arrows represents the strength of the correlation between the prokaryotic community composition and environmental properties. Abbreviations for CS3 are: Ctrl, control with conventional potato treatment; Alt1Pot, alternative crop rotation 1 in the potato field; Alt2Pot, alternative crop rotation 2 in the potato field. Abbreviations for CS4 are: Ctrl, control with conventional P fertilization in potato; MycPotHP, mycorrhizal inoculant plus half the P fertilization in potato; MycNoP, mycorrhizal inoculant with no P fertilization in potato; PotHP, half the P fertilization in potato; PotNoP, potato field with no P fertilization. Abbreviations for CS5 are: Ctrl, pest alert system control in potato; ConvPotFA, conventional fungicide application in potato; PotNoFA, potato without fungicide application.

Case Studies 6, 7, 8 and 9 – Atlantic Central region

As reported in D5.2, only the prokaryotic communities of Case Studies 8 and 9 were significantly impacted by their respective treatments in the Atlantic Central region. In Case Study 8, a clear separation was observed between organic and conventional treatment samples (Figure 1.3). Several environmental parameters were associated with this shift in community composition, including crop yield, exchangeable elements (Mgex, Naex, Caex), pH, organic matter, organic carbon (POC, TOC), CEC, and bioavailable metals (Bba, Moba, Cuba). Only bioavailable iron (Feba) and aggregate size distribution (Agstd_d, 53–250 μm) had a positive relationship with the organic treatment samples. Surprisingly, only a few of the top 40 most abundant genera were associated with some of the environmental properties, including *IS-40*, *Solibacillus*, and *Geobacter* (Figure A1.8). In Case Study 9,

the treatment effect was less clear, but pH, yield, Nt, Pav, and Agsd_c were significantly associated with the community composition. None of the top 40 genera exhibited significant correlations with environmental properties in Case Study 9 (Figure A1.9). In Case Study 6, treatment did not influence community composition, but several parameters were associated with the established configurations, including Fma, organic carbon (TOC, POC), pH, OM, CEC, sum of bases (Bs), and exchangeable elements (Caex, Mgex). For Case Study 7, no environmental parameters were significantly linked to the community compositions. The top 40 genera in Case Studies 6 and 7 exhibited limited associations with the environmental properties (Figures A1.6 and A1.7).

1.3. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the prokaryotic Amplicon sequence variant (ASV) composition of case studies 6, 7, 8 and 9 (CS6, CS7, CS8 and CS9, respectively) implemented in the Atlantic Central pedoclimatic region. Vectors (red arrows) represent environmental variables that were significantly associated with the observed variations in prokaryotic community compositions ($p < 0.05$). The length of the arrows represents the strength of the correlation between the prokaryotic community composition and environmental properties. Abbreviations for CS6: Ctrl = control = conventional farming with cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated, FYM = with farm yard manure; AFV = cover crop mowed and removed; AFVFYM = cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure; AFVbrFYM = cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material; brFYM = farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material (e.g., grass clippings from nature reserves). Abbreviations for CS7 are: Ctrl, standard conditions for potato as control; PhaEgClov, Phacelia and Egyptian clover as cover crops for potato; Mix5, mixture of 5 cover crop species for potato; Mix12, mixture of 12 cover crop species for potato. Abbreviations for CS8 are: OrgInt, organic intensive farming for vegetables; OrgExt, organic extensive farming for vegetables; ConvInt, conventional intensive farming for vegetables; ConvExt, conventional extensive farming

for vegetables. Abbreviations for CS9 are: Ctrl, control wheat field without manure; Comp, composted green manure for wheat; FYM, farmyard manure for wheat; Ferm, fermented green manure for wheat.

Case Studies 10a, 10b and 11 – Continental region

The prokaryotic community composition was not significantly impacted by treatment in any of the Case Studies in the Continental region, as reported in D5.2. However, several environmental parameters were associated with the community composition in Case Study 10a, suggesting that heterogeneity in environmental properties across the case study may contribute to heterogeneity in community constellations (Figure 1.4). The significant environmental parameters included pH, CaCO₃ content, bioavailable metals (Feba, Cuba, Bba), exchangeable elements (Caex, Mgex), and aggregate size distribution (Agds_c, Agsd_d, Agsd_b). In Case Study 10b, only pH (KCl) and bulk density were associated with community composition, while no associations were found for Case Study 11. When exploring the top most abundant genera, *Candidatus Udeabacter*, *Pseudolabrys*, *Steroidobacter*, and *Gaiella* were significantly associated with several environmental parameters in Case Study 10a (Figure A1.10). No associations were observed between top genera and environmental parameters in Case Studies 10a and 11 (Figures A1.11 and A1.12).

Figure 1.4. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the prokaryotic Amplicon sequence variant (ASV) composition of case studies 10a, 10b, and 11 (CS10a, CS10b and CS11, respectively) implemented in the Continental pedoclimatic region. Vectors (red arrows) represent environmental variables that were significantly associated with the observed variations in prokaryotic community compositions ($p < 0.05$). The length of the arrows represents the strength of the correlation between the prokaryotic community

composition and environmental properties. Abbreviations for CS10a are: Ctrl, conventional wheat cultivation with reduced fungicides as control; Biostim, conventional wheat cultivation with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S), and reduced fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat cultivation with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S), plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G), and reduced fungicides. Abbreviations for CS10b are: Ctrl, standard crop management for potato as control; StripUndSow, cultivation with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, cultivation with broad undersowing. Abbreviations for CS11 are: Ctrl, conventional wheat farming as control; ExtWhw, extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and without pesticides; DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and clover undersowing without pesticides.

Case Studies 12 – Nemoral region

In Case Study 12 of the Nemoral region, the sample size was too small to infer treatment effects. However, pH was significantly associated with the prokaryotic community compositions of the case study (Figure 1.5). No associations between the top 40 most abundant genera and environmental parameters were found (Figure A1.13).

Figure 1.5. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the prokaryotic Amplicon sequence variant (ASV) composition of case study 12 (CS12) implemented in the Nemoral pedoclimatic region. Vectors (red arrows) represent environmental variables that were significantly associated with the observed variations in prokaryotic community compositions ($p < 0.05$). The length of the arrows represents the strength of the correlation between the prokaryotic community composition and environmental properties. Abbreviations: Ctrl, conventional wheat farming as control; OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage; ConvNoTill, conventional farming without tillage. FieldEdge, conditions in the edge of the field.

Case Studies 13, 14 and CS15 – Boreal region

The prokaryotic community composition was not impacted by treatment in any of the Case Studies in the Boreal region. However, some environmental parameters were significantly associated with community composition (Figure 1.6). In Case Study 14a, these included pH, bioavailable metals (Znba, Bba, Mnba), yield, sand content (SA), and available phosphorus (Pav). In Case Study 14b, associated environmental parameters included pH, CaCO₃, silt content (SI), clay content (CL), exchangeable

elements (Mgex, Caex), CEC, and particulate organic carbon (POC). In Case Study 15, associated parameters included sand content (SA), clay content (CL), NO₃, exchangeable elements (Mgex, Caex), and bioavailable metals (Cuba, Bba). Only limited associations between environmental parameters and top abundant genera were detected across the case studies (Figures A1.14–A1.17).

Figure 1.6. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the prokaryotic Amplicon sequence variant (ASV) composition of case studies 13, 14a, 14b and 15 (CS13, CS14a, CS14b and CS15, respectively) implemented in the Boreal pedoclimatic region. Vectors (red arrows) represent environmental variables that were significantly associated with the observed variations in prokaryotic community compositions ($p < 0.05$). The length of the arrows represents the strength of the correlation between the prokaryotic community composition and environmental properties. Abbreviations for CS13 are: Ctrl, conventional potato farming without amendments as control; FS, nutrient-poor wood fiber sludge as amendment; CPMS, nutrient-rich composted pulp mill sludge as amendment. Abbreviations for CS15 are: Ctrl, conventional potato farming without cover crops; pha, Phacelia as cover crop after early potato harvest; rye, mixture of rye grass as cover crop after early potato harvest. Abbreviations for CS14a are: Ctrl, organic spring wheat farming with minimum tillage in spring; plough, organic spring wheat farming with ploughing tillage in spring. Abbreviations for CS14b are: Ctrl, organic winter wheat farming with minimum tillage in autumn; plough, organic winter wheat farming with ploughing tillage in autumn.

1.3.2 Relationship between soil ecosystem services and functional gene abundance

Case Studies 1 and 2 – Mediterranean South region

In the Mediterranean region, as reported in D5.2, only some of the targeted functional genes (namely *nirK* and *cbbL*), were significantly impacted by the applied treatment in Case Study 1. Further multivariate analysis showed that the abundance of all the studied functional groups was significantly associated with MDS (Figure 1.7). When exploring potential correlations with each particular gene,

strong positive correlations were found between the *nirK* gene content and MDS and pH, while soil particulate organic carbon (POC) was strongly positively correlated with *nifH*, MDS and soil total organic carbon (TOC) with *ureC*, and cation exchange capacity (CEC) and exchangeable cations content (Mg_{ex} and K_{ex}), with GH7 (Figure 1.8). For Case Study 2, no significant differences were found between treatments and the content of the different functional genes (Deliverable 5.2). However POC and pHCaCl were significantly explaining the variation of all the functional genes in the same direction (Figure 1.7), being POC and Mg_{ex} particularly strongly correlated to the *nifH* gene content, while K_{ex} to the content of the *ureC* gene (Figure 1.9).

Figure 1.7. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plot from South Mediterranean case studies CS1 and CS2 showing the functional gene abundance of the field sites with environmental variables from the last monitoring year. Vectors represent environmental variables that were significantly associated with the observed variations in functional genes ($p < 0.05$). The length of the arrows represents the strength of the correlation between the functional gene abundance and environmental properties. Abbreviations for CS1 are: Ctrl, control with conventional chemical fertilization treatment; fert50, reduced chemical fertilization by 50 %; red50Nuve, reduced chemical fertilization by 50 % with “Nuve” (fungi + bacteria) inoculant; red50Bacto, with “Bactoneco” (PGPB) inoculant. Abbreviations for CS2 are org70, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% with bacterial inoculant; org70BioBa, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% with bacterial and fungal inoculants.

Figure 1.8. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS1 field in the Mediterranean South region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Figure 1.9. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and *GH7*) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS2 field in the Mediterranean South region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Case Studies 3, 4 and 5 – Lusitanian region

In the Lusitanian case studies (CS3, CS4 and CS5), no statistical differences were detected between control and treatments (Deliverable 5.2). Nevertheless, in Case Study 3, a myriad of environmental parameters were significantly linked with all the functional groups including pH (pH, pHCaCl and pHKCl), available phosphorus (Pav), aggregate size distribution (Agsd_c and Agsd_e), bulk density (BD), organic matter (OM), soil total organic carbon (TOC), MDS, actual field moisture content (Fma), cation exchange capacity (CEC), sum of bases (Bs), exchangeable cations (Mg_{ex}, Ca_{ex} and Na_{ex}), and bioavailable Fe (Fe_{ba}) (Figure 1.10). Surprisingly, most of these parameters were strongly positively correlated with all of the targeted functional genes except for *amoA* (Figure 1.11). Similarly, for Case Study 4, many environmental parameters were associated with the functional potential groups, which including OM, TOC, total nitrogen (Nt), MDS, Fma, Bs, exchangeable cations such as Mg_{ex}, K_{ex} and Na_{ex}, and bioavailable Fe (Fe_{ba}), which significantly explained the variation of the total functional groups in the same direction, while pH and Agsd_c, significantly explained the variation of the total functional groups in different directions (Figure 1.10). Most of these parameters were strongly positively correlated with all of the genes, except for Agsd_c, that presented a strong negative correlation (Figure 1.12). In Case Study 5, only nitrate (NO₃) was significantly correlated with all the community (Figure 1.10). However, several variables such as MDS, pH, OM, TOC, soil particulate organic carbon (POC), Nt, Na_{ex}, Bs, ammonium (NH₄), and Agsd_e were strongly positively correlated to most of the genes (Figure 1.13).

Figure 1.10. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plot from the Lusitanian region case studies CS3, CS4 and CS5 showing the functional gene abundance of the field sites with soil environmental variables from the last monitoring year. Vectors represent environmental variables that were significantly associated with the observed variations in functional genes ($p < 0.05$). The length of the arrows represents the strength of the correlation between the functional gene abundance and environmental properties. Abbreviations for CS3 are: Ctrl, control with conventional potato treatment; Alt1Pot, alternative crop rotation 1 in the potato field; Alt2Pot, alternative crop rotation 2 in the potato field. Abbreviations for CS4 are: Ctrl, control with conventional P fertilization in potato; MycPotHP, mycorrhizal inoculant plus half the P fertilization in potato; MycNoP, mycorrhizal inoculant with no P fertilization in potato; PotHP, half the P fertilization in potato; PotNoP, potato field with no P fertilization. Abbreviations for CS5 are: Ctrl, pest alert system control in potato; ConvPotFA, conventional fungicide application in potato; PotNoFA, potato without fungicide application.

Figure 1.11. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbl* and GH7) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS3 field in the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Figure 1.12. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and *GH7*) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS4 field in the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Figure 1.13. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and *GH7*) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS5 field in the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Case Studies 6, 7, 8 and 9 – Atlantic Central region

In the Atlantic Central region, no statistical differences between treatments and control were detected in any of the six functional genes studied in Case Study 6 (Deliverable 5.2). Nevertheless, the total content of functional groups was significantly explained by soil particulate organic carbon (POC) and actual field moisture content (Fma) in different directions (Figure 1.14). When looking into the association with each particular gene, other parameters like exchangeable K (K_{ex}), nitrate (NO_3), bioavailable Mo (Moba), and aggregate size distribution *Agsd_c*, were strongly positively correlated with most of the functional genes (Figure 1.15). Regarding Case Study 7, both *nirK* and *ureC* gene content was significantly impacted by the applied treatment. When looking at the overall groups, however, only MDS contributed to significantly explain the variations found (Figure 1.14). It is also worth noting that Yield was strongly positively correlated to the abundances of the *nirK*, *ureC*, and *cbbL* genes (Figure 1.16). Case Study 8, also presented significant differences between control and treatments in the abundance of genes *amoA*, *nirK*, and *GH7*, as reported in D5.2. As Figure 1.14 depicts, many were associated with this variation. This would include exchangeable elements (Mgex and Caex), soil organic matter (OM), soil organic carbon (POC, TOC), cation exchange capacity (CEC), and bioavailable metals (Moba, Cuba, and Znba), sum of bases (Bs), electrical conductivity (EC), MDS, aggregate size distribution (*Agsd_e*) and calcium carbonate content ($CaCO_3$) in one direction, and bulk density (BD) and aggregate size distribution (*Agsd_d*) in the opposite direction. When exploring potential correlations between each of the genes and the environmental variables not only these parameters, but also Yield and tuber weight (FWEIG) were strongly positively correlated with all the genes except for *nifH* (Figure 1.17). In Case Study 9, no treatment effects were observed as presented in D5.2, but further analysis, revealed that Yield explained a shift when taking into consideration all the groups (Figure 1.14). Furthermore, Fma and ammonium (NH_4), positively correlated with *cbbL* and *GH7*, and *nifH* and *ureC*, respectively (Figure 1.18).

Figure 1.14. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plot from the Atlantic Central region case studies CS6, CS7, CS8 and CS9 showing the functional gene abundance of the field sites with soil environmental variables from the last monitoring year. Vectors represent environmental variables that were significantly associated with the observed variations in functional genes ($p < 0.05$). The length of the arrows represents the strength of the correlation between the functional gene abundance and environmental properties. Abbreviations for CS6 are: Ctrl = control = conventional farming with cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated, FYM = with farm yard manure; AFV = cover crop mowed and removed; AFVFYM = cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure; AFVbrFYM = cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material; brFYM = farm yard manure composted with 'brown' material (e.g., grass clippings from nature reserves). Abbreviations for CS7 are: Ctrl, standard conditions for potato as control; PhaEgClov, Phacelia and Egyptian clover as cover crops for potato; Mix5, mixture of 5 cover crop species for potato; Mix12, mixture of 12 cover crop species for potato. Abbreviations for CS8 are: OrgInt, organic intensive farming for vegetables; OrgExt, organic extensive farming for vegetables; ConvInt, conventional intensive farming for vegetables; ConvExt, conventional extensive farming for vegetables. Abbreviations for CS9 are: Ctrl, control wheat field without manure; Comp, composted green manure for wheat; FYM, farmyard manure for wheat; Ferm, fermented green manure for wheat.

Figure 1.15. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*,

nifH, *ureC*, *cbbl* and GH7) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS6 field in the Atlantic Central region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Figure 1.16. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbl* and GH7) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS7 field in the Atlantic Central region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Figure 1.17. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbl* and GH7) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS8 field in the Atlantic Central region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Figure 1.18. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbl* and GH7) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS9 field in the Atlantic Central region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Case Studies 10a, 10b and 11 – Continental region

None of the Continental Case Studies (CS10a, CS10b and CS11) presented statistical differences between applied treatments, as reported in D5.2. However, several environmental parameters were significantly associated with the distribution of all functional groups in Case Study 10. These included, in one direction, bioavailable metals Feba and Cuba, and, in the opposite direction, MDS, sum of bases (Bs), cation exchange capacity (CEC), exchangeable Ca (Ca_{ex}), pH (pH and pHKCl) and bioavailable Zn (Znba) (Figure 1.19). These variables, together with Yield, electrical conductivity (EC), soil organic matter (OM), total nitrogen (Nt), exchangeable Mg and K (Mg_{ex} and K_{ex}), and actual field moisture content (Fma) were strongly positively correlated with all the genes except for GH7 (Figure 1.20). In Case Study 10b, variations across all the genes abundances were significantly attributed to Bs, Mg_{ex}, CEC, Ca_{ex},

and pHKCl in one direction, and available phosphorus (Pav) in a different direction (Figure 1.19) Moreover, MDS was found to strongly positively correlate to *cbbL*, while soil organic matter (OM) and available Cu (Cuba) to *nifH* (Figure 1.21). Finally, in Case Study 11, only Mg_{ex} , Fma and aggregate size distribution (Agsd_d), each of them in a different direction, significantly impacted the overall genes abundances (Figure 1.19). However, other environmental parameters which included OM, CEC, K_{ex} , Mg_{ex} , Bs and Fma, were strongly positively correlated to the *nifH* gene (Figure 1.22).

Figure 1.19. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plot from the Continental region case studies CS10a, CS10b and CS11 showing the functional gene abundance of the field sites with soil environmental variables from the last monitoring year. Vectors represent environmental variables that were significantly associated with the observed variations in functional genes ($p < 0.05$). The length of the arrows represents the strength of the correlation between the functional gene abundance and environmental properties. Abbreviations for CS10a are: Ctrl, conventional wheat cultivation with reduced fungicides as control; Biostim, conventional wheat cultivation with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S), and reduced fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat cultivation with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S), plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G), and reduced fungicides. Abbreviations for CS10b are: Ctrl, standard crop management for potato as control; StripUndSow, cultivation with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, cultivation with broad undersowing. Abbreviations for CS11 are: Ctrl, conventional wheat farming as control; ExtWhw, extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and without pesticides; DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and clover undersowing without pesticides.

Figure 1.20. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS10a field in the Continental region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Figure 1.21. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS10b field in the Continental region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Figure 1.22. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS11 field in the Continental region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Case Study 12 – Nemoral region

In the Nemoral region, Case Study 12 sample size was too small to conduct statistics as reported in D5.2. Nevertheless, bioavailable Mn (Mnba) was significantly associated with the variation of the overall functional groups (Figure 1.23). Furthermore, actual field moisture content (Fma) and ammonium (NH4), strongly positively correlated to all the genes (Figure 1.24).

Figure 1.23. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plot from the Nemoral region case study CS12 showing the functional gene abundance of the field sites with soil environmental variables from the last monitoring year. Vectors represent environmental variables that were significantly associated with the observed variations in functional genes ($p < 0.05$). The length of the arrows represents the strength of the correlation between the functional gene abundance and environmental properties. Abbreviations for CS12 are: Ctrl, conventional wheat farming as control; OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage; ConvNoTill, conventional farming without tillage. FieldEdge, conditions in the edge of the field.

Figure 1.24. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbl* and GH7) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS12 field in the Nemoral region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Case Studies 13, 14 and CS15 – Boreal region

In Boreal Case Studies, no statistical differences between treatments and control were detected in CS13 and CS14a (Deliverable 5.2). Following a further multivariate analysis, no associations were observed neither between functional gene abundances and environmental parameters (results not shown). However, when exploring correlations with each of the specific genes, multiple positive strong correlation were observed between all the genes except for GH7 and the following environmental parameters: nitrous oxide (N₂O), MDS, electrical conductivity (EC), soil total organic carbon (TOC), total nitrogen (Nt), cation exchange capacity (CEC), exchangeable cations (Na_{ex}, Ca_{ex}, Mg_{ex} and K_{ex}), sum of bases (Bs), actual field moisture content (Fma), nitrate (NO₃), and bioavailable metals (Feba, Moba, and Bba) (Figure 1.26). In Case Study 14a, fewer correlations were found, which included positive strong correlations between *amoA* content and MDS, *nifH* and Na_{ex} and calcium carbonate (CaCO₃), *cbbl* and methane (CH₄) and bioavailable Mn (Mnba), and GH7 and carbon dioxide (CO₂) and aggregate size distribution (Agstd_d) (Figure 1.27). In CS14b, the abundance of *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbl*, and GH7 genes was impacted by ploughing tillage, but only nitrates (NO₃) stood out as a significant environmental variable driving a shift in the overall distribution of functional groups

(Figure 1.25). This parameter, was positively correlated with all of the genes as shown in Figure 1.28. In Case Study 15, only the *ureC* gene was significantly impacted by the treatments applied. However, pH (both pHCaCl and pHKCl) and Yield, explained the variation of the overall abundance (Figure 1.25). Positive strong correlations were found between the *amoA*, *nirK*, and *nifH* genes and several environmental parameters including Nt, several exchangeable elements, Bs and Bba, while CH₄ was strongly correlated to *cbbL* and GH7 genes (Figure 1.29).

Figure 1.25. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plot from the Boreal region case studies CS13, CS14a, CS14b and CS15 showing the functional gene abundance of the field sites with soil environmental variables from the last monitoring year. Vectors represent environmental variables that were significantly associated with the observed variations in functional genes ($p < 0.05$). The length of the arrows represents the strength of the correlation between the functional gene abundance and environmental properties. Abbreviations for CS13 are: Ctrl, conventional potato farming without amendments as control; FS, nutrient-poor wood fiber sludge as amendment; CPMS, nutrient-rich composted pulp mill sludge as amendment. Abbreviations for CS14a are: Ctrl, organic spring wheat farming with minimum tillage in spring; plough, organic spring wheat farming with ploughing tillage in spring. Abbreviations for CS14b are: Ctrl, organic winter wheat farming with minimum tillage in autumn; plough, organic winter wheat farming with ploughing tillage in autumn. Abbreviations for CS15 are: Ctrl, conventional potato farming without cover crops; pha, Phacelia as cover crop after early potato harvest; rye, mixture of rye grass as cover crop after early potato harvest.

Figure 1.26. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS13 field in the Boreal region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Figure 1.27. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS14a field in the Boreal region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Figure 1.28. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS14b field in the Boreal region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Figure 1.29. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the six functional genes (*amoA*, *nirK*, *nifH*, *ureC*, *cbbL* and GH7) and environmental variables from the last monitoring year of CS15 field in the Boreal region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

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2 Fungal diversity

2.1. Introduction

Fungi play a crucial role in agroecosystems by contributing to key ecosystem services in soil, such as decomposing diverse organic compounds, maintaining soil structure and water balance, producing plant growth-promoting substances, and serving as biological controls against disease-causing pathogens (Frąc et al., 2018). However, not all fungi are benign; climate warming is projected to increase the abundance of soil-borne fungal pathogens that threaten plants (Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2020). Conversely, symbiotic soil fungi may enhance ecosystem resilience under climate change conditions (Martínez-García et al., 2017). Disruptions or imbalances in fungal communities can negatively impact carbon and nutrient cycling and soil structure, which may in turn affect soil and plant health, crop yields, and lead to economic losses.

Agricultural practices alter soil chemical and physical properties, thereby affecting soil biology and also fungal communities. It has been suggested that agricultural management strategies aiming to restore fungal biodiversity could reduce chemical, biological, and ecological degradation in arable soils and mitigate nutrient and carbon loss, soil erosion, acidification, pollution, and desertification (Hannula and Morriën, 2022). This section of the report presents findings on the relationships among soil fungal biodiversity, crop yield and quality, and ecosystem service delivery (e.g., greenhouse gas emissions, carbon content, nutrients, bulk density, soil pH, and other soil chemical and physical parameters) derived from WP5 case studies across six European regions. Results are presented from the last monitoring period, with data reported separately for each case study.

2.2. Material and Methods

2.2.1 DNA extractions and sequencing

DNA extraction and sequencing of fungal ITS region was conducted similar to previous report D3.2 according to protocol described in the D3.1 Handbook (Lloret et al., 2020).

2.2.2 Bioinformatics

Raw fungal ITS sequence data was processed with Pipegraph version 2.0 following the OTU pipeline workflow with same parameters used in the previous report D3.2. Raw reads and reads after processing are reported in the previous report D5.3.

2.2.3 Community and statistical analyses

All fungal analyses were conducted using RStudio (version 2023.9.0.463; Posit Team 2023) and R (version 4.4.0; R Core Team 2024). The composition of fungal taxa for each case study was analyzed with the phyloseq package, employing the functions *prune_taxa* and *aggregate_rare* at the Family level, with a detection threshold of 0.02 and a prevalence criterion of two samples out of the total sample count. Figures were created using the *ggplot2* (Wickham, 2016) and *phyloseq* (McMurdie & Holmes, 2013) R packages. Alpha diversity metrics were obtained from the phyloseq objects using

the *microeco* R package (Liu et al., 2021). Fungal guilds were assigned from taxonomically parsed fungal OTU data using FUNGuild, facilitated by a Python-based tool (Nguyen et al., 2016).

Relationships between soil physicochemical and environmental properties (listed Appendix Table 1.1), dominant fungal genera, and alpha diversity metrics were examined using Spearman's rank correlations, with results visualized as heatmaps (Spearman, 1987). For Spearman's rank analyses, representative soil physicochemical and environmental properties were selected, excluding those with strong autocorrelation (correlation coefficients < -0.7 or > 0.7).

Beta diversity of the total fungal community, as well as saprotrophic, pathotrophic, and symbiotrophic sub-communities, was assessed using non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) or a transformation-based version of principal component analysis (tb-PCA) based on OTU relative abundances (calculated as proportions of total reads in each sample library). These analyses were conducted in conjunction with measured soil physical and chemical properties (listed in Appendix Table 1.1) using the *envfit* function from the *vegan* package. When available, data on crop yield, quality, and greenhouse gas fluxes were fitted as well. Variables significantly influencing community composition variation ($p < 0.05$) were displayed in the NMDS or tb-PCA plots. NMDS was performed with stable solutions from random starts, axis scaling, and species scores using the *metaMDS* function in the *vegan* package (version 2.5-5; *vegan*: Community Ecology Package, 2012; Oksanen et al. 2019) with Bray-Curtis dissimilarity. If NMDS produced near-zero stress, tb-PCA was applied, in which abundance data were log-transformed before Hellinger standardization. Multivariate analyses were complemented with permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) on Bray-Curtis distance matrices, using the *adonis2* function from the *vegan* package (Anderson, 2001), and pairwise comparisons were conducted with *pairwise.adonis* in *vegan*.

2.3. Results and discussion

2.3.1 Interrelationship between soil ecosystem services and dominant taxa

None of the soil derived factor within the treatment showed relationship with the the most dominant fungal taxa ($n=50$) in CS1 field. However, irrespective of the treatment two genera belonging to important saprotrophs of plant derived material, *Humicola* and *Corynascus*, and family Bionectriaceae Incertea sedis (uncertain position in taxa) containing saprotrophs and pathogens showed negative correlations with cation exchange capacity of the soil (CEC) (Figure 2.1). CEC is an important soil indicator which represents soil's ability to hold onto essential nutrients and to buffer against soil acidification.

Figure 2.1. The heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the most abundant genera and greenhouse gases and soil physicochemical properties from the last monitoring year of CS1 field in the Mediterranean South region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix X.

None of the soil derived factors within the treatment showed relationship with the the most dominant fungal taxa in CS2. However, irrespective of the treatments saprotrophic and pathogenic *Ascochyta* and plant pathogen *Pseudoarthrographis* showed negative correlations with calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) and nitrate (NO_3), respectively (Figure 2.2). There is evidence that both nitrate and CaCO_3 availability may have a role to promote antifungal activities of some fungal pathogens (Knox et al. 2000, Liu et al. 2023).

Figure 2.2. The heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the most abundant genera and soil physicochemical properties from the last monitoring year of CS2 field in the Mediterranean South region. Abbreviations are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

None of the soil derived factors within the treatment showed relationship with the the most dominant fungal taxa in CS3. However, respective of the treatments there were a few taxa that showed relationship to measured factors. Genus *Trichoderma* showed negative correlations with CEC and concentration of magnesium (Mg) (Figure 2.3). Species of *Trichoderma* have potential as biocontrollers of fungal and nematode pathogens and inducers of plant systemic disease resistance (Brunner et al. 2005, Yao et al. 2023). In contrast, saprotrophic soil yeast *Saitozyma* showed positive correlation with CEC, and concentrations of Mg and iron (Fe). High amounts of auxin (IAA) which is the most common plant hormone regulating plant growth and development have been detected in *Saitozyma podzolica* (Streletskii et al., 2016). In addition, another two genera with saprotrophic soil yeasts *Lipomyces* and *Vishniacozyma* showed positive correlation with Mg, and genus with unknown ecological role *Extremopsis* and Aspergillaceae Incertae sedis with concentration of copper (Cu). High CEC enables to retain Mg in soil particles for the use of plants. Since Mg has central role in plant chlorophyll and activation of specific enzyme systems, its deficiency can lead to decreased plant growth. Cu is needed in small quantities for the development of crops.

Figure 2.3. The heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the most abundant genera and soil physicochemical properties from the last monitoring year of CS3 field in the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Chaetothyriales Incertae sedis showed strong positive correlation with CaCO₃ and negative correlation with concentration of molybdenum (Mo) in the potato plots without phosphorus fertilization (PotNoP) in CS4 (Figure 2.4). Chaetothyriales order is particularly known for the black yeast, but ecology and habitats of species are highly diverse (Quan et al. 2020).

Figure 2.4. The heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the most abundant genera and soil physicochemical properties from the last monitoring year of CS4 field in the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations for the treatments: Ctrl, control with conventional potato farming; MycPotHP, potato plots with mycorrhizal inoculant + half less P fertilization; MycNoP, potato plots with mycorrhizal inoculant without P fertilization; PotHP, potato plots with half less P fertilization; PotNoP, potato plots without P fertilization. Abbreviations are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

Genus *Tetragoniomyces* including fungal parasites showed strong negative correlation with CaCO_3 in the potato plots without fungicide application (PotNoFA) (Figure 2.5). Thus, decreased amount of CaCO_3 might have potential to increased this parasite when chemical plant protection agents are not used, since availability of CaCO_3 are known to promote antifungal activities (Liu et al. 2023).

Figure 2.5. The heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the most abundant genera and soil physicochemical properties from the last monitoring year of CS5 field in the Lusitanian region. Abbreviations for the treatments: Ctrl, potato plots with pest alert system; ConvPotFA, potato plots with conventional fungicide application; PotNoFA, potato plots without fungicide application. Abbreviations are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

None of the soil derived factors within the treatment showed relationship with the the most dominant fungal taxa in CS6. However, irrespective of the treatments there were several taxa that showed relationship to measured factors. Several taxa showed negative or positive relationship with total organic soil carbon (TOC) (Figure 2.6). Those having negative correlations with TOC included soil saprotroph *Emericellopsis*, plant pathogen *Ilyonectria*, common plant pathogenic and endophytic *Fusarium*, dung saprotroph *Schizothecium*, plant and wood saprotroph *Pseudophialocephala*, *Exophiala* with many roles as pathogen, plant saprotroph and dark septate endophyte, *Extremopsis*, common saprotrophs and endophytes containing *Mortierella*, and Helotiales Incertae sedis. *Exophiala* contain dark-septate endophytes that have potential to increase the tolerance of their host plants to abiotic stresses (Khan et al., 2012; Li et al., 2011a; Li et al., 2011b). In contrast those having positive correlations with TOC included plant pathogens, saprotrophs and endophytes containing *Paecilomyces*, common plant saprotrophs and pathogens containing *Gibellulopsis*, *Verticillium* with many roles as pathogens, endophytes and saprotrophs, endophytic and fungal parasitic *Papulaspora*,

plant saprotroph *Botryotrichum* and soil saprotroph *Chordomyces*. Genera *Extremopsis* and *Mortierella* had also negative and genera *Verticillium* and *Chordomyces* positive correlations with potassium (K). Genera *Paecilomyces* and *Gibellulopsis* had positive correlation with CEC and soil pH, respectively. Some strains of *Gibellulopsis* are reported to induce resistance against some plant pathogens (Hao et al. 2022). Thus, these results indicate that different fertilization treatments including diverse set of manure and co-composted straw and cover crop mowing and mixing might have affected several fungi especially via changes in TOC.

Figure 2.6. The heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the most abundant genera and soil physicochemical properties from the last monitoring year of CS6 field in the Atlantic Central region. Abbreviations are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

None of the soil derived factors showed correlations with the most dominant fungal taxa tested with or without treatments with in CS7. None of the soil derived factors within the treatment showed relationship with the most dominant fungal taxa in CS8. However, irrespective of the treatments several taxa that showed relationship to measured factors. Several taxa showed negative or positive relationship with soil pH, CEC and the smallest soil aggregate size distribution class < 53 (Agsd_e) (Figure 2.7). Those having negative correlations with those three included genera *Fusarium*, and three saprotrophic genera *Chordomyces*, *Aaosphaeria* and *Psathyrella*, and those with positive

correlations included several general soil saprotrophic genera *Neocosmospora*, *Dichotomopilus* and *Striatibotrys*, as well as more specialized saprotrophs *Schizothecium* for dung, *Trechispora* for wood, and genera with various roles as pathogen and plant and dung saprotroph and endophytic genus *Microascus* and endophytic, plant pathogenic and saprotrophic *Plectosphaerella*. The latter includes the species causing potato wilt disease (Gao et al. 2016). Genera *Psathyrella*, *Striatibotrys*, and pathogenic and saprotrophic *Didymella* showed negative correlation with POC, BD and Agsd_e, respectively. Genus *Mortierella* showed negative, while genera *Arthrographis* and *Saitozyma* showed positive correlation with soil pH. Rozellomycota Incertae sedis, *Chaetomium* with many roles as pathogen, saprotroph for various materials and endophyte, and Sordariomycetes Incertae sedis showed positive correlation with Agsd_e. Genera lichen parasite *Minimedusa*, endophytic fungal parasitic and wood saprotrophic *Papulaspora* and pollen saprotroph *Operculomyces* showed positive correlations with K, whereas genera *Cladorrhinum* and *Chaetomium* with multiple roles as animal and plant pathogen, dung saprotroph, endophyte and plant and wood saprotroph, plant pathogenic and saprotrophic *Stemphylium* and Chaetomiaceae, Pleosporaceae and Sordariomycetes Incertae sedis showed negative correlations with K. In addition, saprotrophic genera *Neocosmospora*, *Schizothecium*, *Dichotomopilus* and *Trechispora* showed negative correlations with Fe. We could not detect direct link between soil derived factors affecting certain fungi in extensive or intensive farming in either organic or conventional management system. However, our results indicate that there are fungi that might respond similarly to small soil aggregate size, soil H and CEC, which is most likely affected by different management. At least small highly-porous soil aggregates benefit plant growth. These three factors are linked, since smaller soil particle size predicts higher CEC (Bi et al. 2023), and increasing soil pH increases also CEC.

Figure 2.7. The heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the most abundant genera and soil physicochemical properties from the last monitoring year of CS8 field in the Atlantic Central region. Abbreviations found in Appendix Table 1.1..

None of the soil derived factors within the treatment showed relationship with the the most dominant fungal taxa in CS9. However, irrespective of the treatments unspecified saprotrophic genus *Chordomyces* showed positive correlation with the amount of nitrate (NO_3). Positive correlations with saprotrophic fungal guilds and soil nitrate have been reported (Geng et al. 2023). In addition, genus containing yeast with several ecological roles *Candida*, saprotrophic genus *Wallemia* and Chaetomiaceae Incertae sedis showed negative correlation with K, Cu and NH_4 , respectively (Figure 2.8). Genus *Wallemia* contains representatives which can tolerate higher concentrations of sugars and salts and thus are adapted to low water availability (Zalar et al. 2005, Kralj et al. 2010).

Figure 2.8. The heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the most abundant genera and soil physicochemical properties from the last monitoring year of CS9 field in the Atlantic Central region. Abbreviations found in Appendix Table 1.1.

None of the soil derived factors within the treatment showed relationship with the the most dominant fungal taxa in CS10a. However, irrespective of the treatments genus containing dung saprotrophs *Schizothecium*, genus *Junewangia* with unknown ecological function and Junewangiaceae Incertae sedis showed negative relationship with soil pH, CEC and boron (B) (Figure 2.9). Linkage between lower abundance of dung saprotrophs and higher CEC from farmlands has been observed (Oliveira et al. 2024). Also, *Junewangia* and Junewangiaceae Incertae sedis showed negative correlation with total nitrogen (Nt). *Schizothecium* was the most abundant genus of Lasiosphaeriaceae family, which had an increasing trend in Biostim treatment in as reported in the earlier report D5.2. Genus *Verticillium* with various roles as animal and plant pathogen as well as endophyte and saprotroph showed a positive correlation with available phosphorus (Pav).

Figure 2.9. The heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the most abundant genera and soil physicochemical properties from the last monitoring year of CS10a field in the Continental region. Abbreviations are found in Appendix Table 1.1.

None of the soil derived factors within or irrespective of the treatment showed relationship with the the most dominant fungal taxa in CS10b, CS11 or CS12 (results not shown).

None of the soil derived factors within the treatment showed relationship with the the most dominant fungal taxa in CS13. However, irrespective of the treatments genus *Neocosmospora* showed a strong negative correlation with CEC (Figure 2.10). The nolys representative of this genus which was detected in CS13, *Neocosmospora rubicola*, causes stem rot of potato affecting negatively potato growth and yield quality. The result is interesting, since CEC is suggested to be one of the most important indicators of soil fertility (Xu et al. 2022), i.e., soil's ability to retain and supply nutrients.

Figure 2.10. The heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the most abundant genera and greenhouse gases and soil physicochemical properties from the last monitoring year of CS13 field in the Boreal region. Abbreviations are found in Appendix X.

None of the soil derived factors within or irrespective of the treatment showed relationship with the the most dominant fungal taxa in CS14a. However, irrespective of the treatments saprotrophic yeast genus *Mrakia* showed a negative correlation with soil electrical conductance (EC) (Figure 2.10). EC affects nutrient availability in soil, thus it has an indirect link to plant growth.

Figure 2.10. The heatmap represents Spearman's correlations between the most abundant genera and greenhouse gases and soil physicochemical properties from the last monitoring year of CS14a field in the Boreal region. Abbreviations for the properties are found in Appendix X.

None of the soil derived factors within the treatment, whereas there were a few taxa among the most dominant ones that showed negative correlation with soil in CS14b (Figure 2.10). Genus *Apiotrichum* showed a negative correlation, whereas *Hypocreales Incertae sedis* and *Botryotrichum* showed a positive one. *Botryotrichum* are common saprotrophs in organic rich soils and potential producers of secondary metabolites (Elkhateeb & Daba, 2022). None of the soil derived factors within

or irrespective of the treatment showed relationship with the most dominant fungal taxa in CS15 (data not shown).

Figure 2.11. The heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the most abundant genera and greenhouse gases and soil physicochemical properties from the last monitoring year of CS14b field in the Boreal region. Abbreviations for the properties are found in Appendix X.

2.3.2 Interrelationship between soil ecosystem services and alpha diversity

None of the soil derived factors with or without the treatment showed correlations with the alpha diversity measures in CS1 or CS2 Lusitanian field sites.

None of the soil derived factors within the treatment showed correlations with the alpha diversity measures in CS3 field. However, irrespective of the treatment, Chao1, Fisher, ACE and se.Ace alpha measures showed negative correlation with carbon dioxide (CO₂) (Figure 2.12). The results might

indicate, that there are only a limited amount of taxa or rare species that are responsible for the soil respiration in CS3.

Figure 2.12. The heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the alpha diversity measures and greenhouse gases and soil physicochemical properties from the last monitoring year of CS3 field in the Mediterranean South region. Abbreviations are found in Appendix Table 1.1..

None of the soil derived factors with or irrespective of the treatment showed relationship with the alpha diversity measures in other Lusitanian case study fields CS4 or CS5.

None of the soil derived factors with or irrespective of the treatment showed relationship with the alpha diversity measures in other Lusitanian case study fields CS6, CS7 or CS9. For CS8 data, when measures were investigated irrespective of the treatment several richness and diversity measures showed negative correlation with the concentration of iron (Fe) and positive correlation with soil pH (Figure 2.13). Observed number of OTUs (Observed) and Fisher index showed positive correlation with CEC. Shannon diversity also showed positive correlation with the proportion of the smallest aggregate size distribution class <53 (Agsd_e). We might suggest that two positive soil health indicator, small soil aggregate size and CEC, have promoted fungal richness and diversity promoted. These results indirectly show that whether fields are managed intensively or extensively under organic or conventional system might have an impact on fungal diversity via soil physical and chemical characteristics, although due to complex data it is difficult to speculate further.

Figure 2.13. The heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between alpha diversity measures and soil physicochemical properties from the last monitoring year of CS8 field in the Atlantic Central region. Abbreviations of the properties are found in Appendix X.

None of the soil derived factors within the treatments or irrespective of the treatment showed relationship with the alpha diversity measures in case studies CS10a, CS10b or CS11 from the Continental region. None of the soil derived factors showed relationship with the alpha diversity measures in case study CS12 from the Nemoral region. Similarly, none of the soil derived factors within or irrespective of the treatment showed relationship with the alpha diversity measures in case studies CS13, CS14a, CS14b or CS15 from the Boreal region.

2.3.3 Interrelationship between soil ecosystem services and beta diversity

As already shown in the earlier report D5.2, total fungal community composition did not differ between control and treatments in either CS1 or CS2. However, CEC and B were significantly explaining the variation in the total fungal community composition in different directions in CS1 (Figure 2.14). In turn, ammonium (NH_4) pointed out to the opposite direction in the ordination than two other variables, available phosphorus (Pav) and calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) that explained the variation in the total fungal community composition in CS2. These soil derived factors may have affected the total fungal community composition indirectly via treatments, but this remains to be unsolved.

Figure 2.14. Two-dimensional non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plot from South Mediterranean case studies CS1 and CS2 showing the fungal community composition of the field sites with soil derived variables from the last monitoring year. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by farming practices (Treatment). Vectors represent significant soil derived variables ($p < 0.05$). Abbreviations: Ctrl, control with conventional chemical fertilization treatment; fert50, reduced chemical fertilization by 50%; red50Nuve, reduced chemical fertilization by 50% with “Nuve” (fungi + bacteria) inoculant; red50Bacto, with “Bactoneco” (PGPB) inoculant; org70, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% with bacterial inoculant; org70BioBa, reduced organic fertilizer by 70% with bacterial and fungal inoculants.

Fungal community composition differed between control and AltPot2 treatment in CS3 (D5.2, Figure 2.25, Table 2.1). In CS3, there were several variables that significantly explained the variation of the total fungal community composition (Figure 2.15). However, none of the variables clearly pointed out to the direction of treatments. Nevertheless, in the left side of the NMDS1 axis indicating more to the treatments included total organic carbon content (TOC), total nitrogen content (Nt), cation exchange capacity in soil (CEC), field moisture (FM), soil organic matter content (OM), concentration of iron (Fe) and the smallest soil aggregate size distribution class (Agsd_e). Thus, these results suggest along with changes in fungal community composition, treatments have promoted positive soil health indicators. Whereas, bulk density of soil (BD) and sand content (SA) explained the variation in the opposite side of the NMDS1 axis. This makes sense, since high bulk density indicates low soil porosity and soil compaction restricting root growth, and movement of air and water. Potassium content (K) showed significance along the NMDS2.

Total fungal community differed also between control and all different fertilization treatments in CS4 (D5.2, Figure 2.25, Table 2.1). In CS4, Pav, TOC, OM, FM, Agsd_e, base saturation (Bs), and concentrations of K, Mg, Ca and Na showed significance along the positive part of the NMDS2 axis towards PotHP treatment, whereas soil pH and the second biggest soil aggregate size distribution class (250–2000) (Agsd_c) showed significance along NMDS2 in the opposite direction. The result suggests that many important nutrient cations as well as total organic carbon and phosphorus along positive physical soil structure indicators may benefit from reduced phosphorus fertilization with or without mycorrhizal inoculants.

In turn, fungal community composition did not differ between control and treatments in CS5 although it had slightly separating trend between control and PotNoFA treatment. Nitrate (NO₃) and soil electrical conductivity (EC) were significantly explaining the variation in the fungal community composition towards the PotNoFA treatment along the PC1 axis, whereas the smallest soil aggregate size distribution class (<53) (Agsd_e) and the content of silt showed significance towards the control treatment along the PC2 axis in CS5. Due to lack of fungicides nitrate may have increased role to promote antifungal activities against fungal pathogens (Knox et al. 2000).

Figure 2.15. Two-dimensional non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plot from the Lusitanian region case studies CS3 and CS4 and and principal component analysis (PCA) plot from CS5 showing the fungal community composition of the field sites with soil derived variables from the last monitoring year. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by farming practices (Treatment). Vectors represent significant soil derived variables ($p < 0.05$). Abbreviations: Ctrl, control with conventional potato farming; Alt1Pot, alternative crop rotation 1 in potato; Alt2Pot, alternative crop rotation2 in potato; ; MycPotHP, potato plots with mycorrhizal inoculant + half less P fertilization; MycNoP, potato plots with mycorrhizal inoculant without P fertilization; PotHP, potato plots with half less P fertilization; PotNoP, potato plots without P

fertilization; ConvPotFA, potato plots with conventional fungicide application; PotNoFA, potato plots without fungicide application.

There was a slight difference in fungal community composition between treatments in CS6 (D5.2 Figure 2.26, Table 2.1). Composition in treatments with AFVFYM and FYM and several variables significantly explained the variation in the total fungal community composition along the NMDS1 axis towards these treatments (Figure 2.16). These variables included clearly field moisture content (FM), total nitrogen content (Nt), total organic carbon content (TOC), electrical conductivity (EC), K content and soil pH. All of these are positive indicators of soil health. As shown in D5.2, fungal community composition did not differ between control and treatments in CS7, CS8 or CS9 fields. However, in CS7 there were two variables that showed significance in the ordination. Content of natrium (Na) showed significance along the NDMS1, whereas available phosphorus (Pav) showed significance along the second NMDS2 axis. In CS8, several variables showed significance along the NMDS1 more towards the conventional farming treatments including copper (Cu), calsium (Ca) and boron (B), OM, Bs, EC, CEC, FM, soil pH, as well as crop yield (Yield). Only two variables indicated significance into opposite direction along the NMDS1 axis more towards organic farming: Fe into the direction of intensive organic farming and the smallest soil aggregate size class into the direction of extensive organic farming treatment. In CS9, TOC, OM, Nt, Pav and B showed significance affecting the variation of the fungal community composition along the NMDS2 axis more towards control treatment, whereas soil pH points out to the opposite direction more towards FYM treatment. Manure application slows the growth of fungi by increasing the soil pH to more neutral range (Liu et al. 2020). Yet, manure induced changes in soil fungal communities have been observed numerous studies (e.g. Ding et al. 2017, Wen et al. 2020, Xiang et al. 2020, Semenov et al. 2022, Su et al. 2022).

Figure 2.16. Two-dimensional non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plots from the Atlantic Central region case studies CS6, CC7, CS8 and CS9 showing the fungal community composition of the field sites with soil derived variables from the last monitoring year. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by farming practices (Treatment). Vectors represent significant soil derived variables ($p < 0.05$). Abbreviations for CS6: Ctrl: conventional farming with cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated without fertilizers; FYM, conventional farming with cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated with farm yard manure; AFV, cover crop mowed and removed without fertilizers; AFVFYM, cover crop mowed and removed plus fertilizer with farm yard manure; AFVbrFYM, cover crop mowed and removed with farm yard manure and “brown” co-composted straw; brFYM, conventional farming with cover crop mix destroyed and incorporated with farm yard manure and “brown” co-composted straw. Abbreviations for CS7: Ctrl: conventional potato farming; PhaEgClov, potato plot with Phacelia and Egyptian clover as cover crop; Mix5, potato plot with mixture of 5 cover crop species; Mix12, potato plots with mixture of 12 cover crop species. Abbreviations for CS8: OrgInt, organic intensive farming for vegetables; OrgExt, organic extensive farming for vegetables; ConvInt, conventional intensive farming for vegetables; ConvExt, conventional extensive farming for vegetables. Abbreviations for CS9: Ctrl: plot without manure; Comp, plot with composted green manure; FYM, plot with farmyard manure; Ferm, plot with fermented green manure.

There was a slightly significant difference in fungal community composition between control and biostimulant treatment plots in CS10a (D5.2 Figure 2.27, Table 2.1). Several variables explained the variation of the total fungal community composition (Figure 2.17) including CEC, EC, Bs, Nt, soil pH, and concentrations of Mg, Ca, K and B. The smallest soil aggregate size distribution class (Agsd_d) showed significance into the opposite direction. There was also a slight difference between controls and both strip and broad undersowing treatments in CS10b. However, none of the environmental soil derived variables explained significantly the variation of the fungal community composition. Fungal communities did not differ between treatments in CS11, whereas there was a slight separating trend between control and DivExtWhe treatment. Soil pH and clay content (CL) were significant soil variables affecting significantly the variation of the fungal community composition, and they pointed out into different directions in the ordination.

Figure 2.17. Two-dimensional principal component analysis (PCA) plots from the Atlantic Central region case studies CS10a and CS10b, and non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plot from CS11 showing the

fungal community composition of the field sites with soil derived variables from the last monitoring year. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by farming practices (Treatment). Vectors represent significant soil derived variables ($p < 0.05$). Abbreviations for CS10a: Ctrl, conventional wheat plot with reduction of fungicides; Biostim, conventional wheat plot with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S) and reduction of fungicides; BiostimAdj, conventional wheat plot with additive (Kantor), plant biostimulant (Nutri Phite Magnum S), plant adjuvant (Smart Seed G) and reduction of fungicides. Abbreviations for CS10b: Ctrl, conventional farming; StripUndSow; plot with strip undersowing; BroadUndSow, plot with broad undersowing. Abbreviations for CS11: Ctrl, conventional wheat farming; ExtWhw; extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and without pesticides; DivExtWhe, diversified extensive wheat farming with wide seed rows and clover undersowing without pesticides.

In CS12, there were only a few soil derived variables that significantly explained the variation in the total fungal community composition (Figure 2.18). In 2022 B was indicating more towards conventional tilled control site. Pav and the second largest soil aggregate distribution class pointed towards the non-cultivated field edge in the last year. Since there was no representative amount of replicates from CS12 field, results can be only indicative.

Figure 2.18. Two-dimensional non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plots from the Nemoral region case study CS12 showing the fungal community composition of the field sites with soil derived variables from the two last monitoring years. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by farming practices (Treatment). Vectors represent significant soil derived variables ($p < 0.05$). Abbreviations for CS12: Ctrl; conventional farming with conventional tillage (winter wheat in 2022, pea in 2023); OrgConvTill, organic farming with conventional tillage (winter wheat in 2022, grass in 2023); ConvNoTillPest, conventional without tillage and with pesticides (spring wheat); ConvNoTill, conventional farming without tillage (*Medicago sativa* as crop plant); FieldEdge, non-cultivated site with wild grasses.

Although treatments did not significantly affect total fungal community composition of any of the four boreal case study field in the last monitoring year, there were several soil derived variables that seem to affect the variation of the fungal community composition (Figure 2.19). In CS13, concentrations of Mg, Na, Ca and B, as well as NO_3 and Nt contents, EC, Bs, N_2O gas and clay (CL) and silt (SI) contents affected the variation along the NMDS2 axis. Whereas starch content of the early potato (STARCON), sand (SA) content and the second largest soil aggregate distribution class (Agdsd_c) pointed out towards the opposite direction along the NMDS2 axis. In CS14a, two variables, concentration of Mg and crop yield (Yield) were the only significant variables affecting the fungal community composition.

In CS14b, there were four variables that pointed out to different directions in the ordination: soil pH, concentration of Mn, as well as POC and Pav which pointed out to same direction. In CS15, concentrations of Na and Ca as well as Bs showed significance along the right side of the NMDS1 axis, whereas sand content (SA) and concentration of Zn showed significance along the opposite side of the NMDS1 axis.

Figure 2.19. Two-dimensional non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plots from the Boreal region case studies CS13, CS14a, CS14b and CS15 showing the fungal community composition of the field sites with soil derived variables from the last monitoring years. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by farming practices (Treatment). Vectors represent significant soil derived variables ($p < 0.05$). Abbreviations for CS13: Ctrl, conventional potato farming without amendments; FS, nutrient-poor wood fiber sludge as amendment; CPMS, nutrient-rich composted pulp mill sludge as amendment. Abbreviations for CS14a: Ctrl, organic spring wheat farming with minimum tillage in spring; plough, organic spring wheat farming with ploughing tillage in spring. Abbreviations for CS14b: Ctrl, organic winter wheat farming with minimum tillage in autumn; plough, organic winter wheat farming with ploughing tillage in autumn. Abbreviations for CS15: Ctrl, conventional early potato farming without cover crops; pha, Phacelia as cover crop after the early potato harvest; rye, mixture of and rye grass as cover crop after the early potato harvest.

2.3.4 Interrelationship between soil ecosystem services and functional guilds

In CS1 or CS2, treatments did not affect significantly the variation of any of the three separate fungal guild community composition. However, field soil moisture (FM) affected significantly the variation of the saprotrophic fungal community composition along the NMDS1 axis towards the treatments in CS1 (Figure 2.20). In CS2, EC and concentration of B were only significant variables affecting the

variation of the saprotrophic community composition. Whereas the variation of the pathotrophic community composition were affected by several variables including grain moisture (Grmoist), CaCO₃, concentrations of Ca, Mg, B and Na, as well as content of NH₄ and silt, and CEC, EC and Bs. Thus, although the direct impacts of agricultural practices on fungal guilds could not be shown, results give indications that there might be indirect effects due to differences in soil physical and chemical conditions between treatments which were not tested simultaneously.

Figure 2.20. Two-dimensional non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) or principal-component (PCA) plots from CS1 and CS2 case studies showing the saprotrophic, pathotrophic and symbiotrophic fungal community composition with soil derived variables from the last monitoring years. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by farming practices (Treatment). Vectors represent significant soil derived variables ($p < 0.05$). See abbreviations in Figures 2.13.

In CS3, treatments did not affect significantly any of the three separate fungal community composition either (Figure 20.21). However, the variation of saprotrophic community composition was explained by bulk density (BD) and sand content (SA) indicated the opposite direction than other variables including silt (SI) and clay (CL) content, OM content, CEC, Pav, Nt, FM, TOC, the smallest soil aggregate distribution class (Agds_e) and concentrations of Fe, Mn and K. The variation of pathotrophic community composition was explained by sand contents (SA) and in the opposite side of the plot, OM, CEC, clay (CL) and silt content (SI), concentration of Fe and the smallest soil aggregate distribution class (Agds_e). In turn, saprotrophic community composition in CS4 differed between control and treatments explaining 35% of the variation ($R^2=0.35682$, $F=2.0804$, $p=0.001$) (Figure 2.20). Pairwise adonis verified the difference ($p=0.41$) which was biggest between control and potato plots with mycorrhizal inoculant without P fertilization (MycNoP, $R^2=0.46$). Variables that explained the variation of the saprotrophic community composition included FM, Bs, CaCO₃ and concentrations of Na, K, Mg, B and Ca. Thus, soil conditions due to treatment may have induced soil saprotrophs that have the potential to release P from insoluble forms in soil (e.g. Ceci et al. 2018). Along with the saprotrophs, less P or P deficiency might have been simulated by mycorrhizal inoculant to help plants

in phosphate uptake and growth. Results reported in the previous report D5.2. are strongly supporting this view. Variables that explained the variation of the pathotrophic community included BS and concentrations of Na, K, B, Ca and Cu. Only soil pH explained the variation of symbiotrophic community composition in CS4. In CS5, community composition of saprotrophs and symbiotrophs did not show statistical difference, whereas there was a difference in community of pathotrophs ($R^2=0.42$, $F=2.18$, $p=0.012$) according to PERMANOVA between control and treatment plots. However, pairwise comparison could not verify this difference anymore although there was a separating trend especially between control plots and potato plots without fungicide application (PotNoFA) ($p=0.15$). The variation of the pathotrophic community composition was explained by the Bs, soil pH and concentration of Ca to the direction of PotNoFa treatment, and to the other directions contents of SI and SA. Yet, there were several variables explaining the variation of saprotrophic community composition including SI and CL content, NO_3 , EC, concentration of Mg and the proportion of the smallest soil aggregate size distribution class (Agsd_e). Symbiotrophs, in turn, was explained by Pav and concentration of Mo.

Figure 2.21. Two-dimensional non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) and principal-component (PCA) plots from CS3, CS4 and CS5 case studies showing the saprotrophic, pathotrophic and symbiotrophic fungal community composition with soil derived variables from the last monitoring years. Different colours

separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by farming practices (Treatment). Vectors represent significant soil derived variables ($p < 0.05$). See abbreviations in Figures 2.14.

In CS6, community composition of saprotrophs and symbiotrophs differed between control and treatment plots according to PERMANOVA (Sap: $R^2=0.32$, $F=1.66$, $p=0.006$; Sym: $R^2=0.27$, $F=1.23$, $p=0.03$). However, pairwise comparison could not verify difference anymore although there was a diverging trend in saprotrophs especially between control plots and plots where cover crop mix was destroyed and incorporated with farm yard manure (FYM) and plots where cover crops were mowed and incorporated with with farm yard manure (AFVFM) ($p=0.08$). Variables that explained the variation of the saprotrophic community composition pointed towards FYM and AFVFM treatments and included EC, FM, TOC, Nt and concentration of K (Figure 2.22). Manure has reported to increase electrical conductivity, organic C, total N and to improve water stable soil aggregates parallel to our results. The variation of pathotrophic and symbiotrophic community composition was explained by FM and EC, respectively.

In CS7, treatments did not affect significantly any of the three separate fungal guild community composition. However, irrespective of the treatments the variation of saprotrophic community composition was explained by crop yield (Yield), CEC, Bs, Pav, concentration of Ca and the proportion of the smallest soil aggregate size distribution class (Agsd_e), and to the opposite direction the proportion of the second largest soil aggregate size distribution class (Agsd_c). In turn, the variation of the pathotrophs was explained by the concentration of Na only.

PERMANOVA showed that there were differences in the community composition of all three different main fungal guilds in CS8. However, pairwise comparison could verify differences only between saprotrophs and symbiotrophs ($p=0.04$). The biggest difference between the saprotrophic community composition was between conventional and organic extensive farming plots ($R^2=0.55$) and least between intensive and extensive plots under both organic and conventional farming system ($R^2=0.25$ and $R^2=0.23$, respectively). Variables that seem to explain the variation of the saprotrophic fungal community in organically farmed plots included sand content (SA) and the proportion of the second smallest soil aggregate size distribution class (Agsd_d). There were numerous variables that seem to be responsible for the variation of the saprotrophic community composition in conventionally farmed plots including CL and SI content, POC, OM, FM, and Cu pointing more towards intensively farmed plots and variables including CEC, EC, Bs, TOC, soil pH, Nt, the proportion of the smallest soil aggregate size distribution class (Agsd_e) and concentration of Ca and Mo more towards extensively farmed plot. Symbiotrophic community composition diverged most between conventional and organic intensive farming plots ($R^2=0.41$) than between conventional and organic extensive farming plots ($R^2=0.28$). Symbiotrophs did not differ between conventional intensive and extensive plots but differed between organic intensive and extensive plots ($R^2=0.26$). Significant variables that seem to explain the variation of the symbiotrophic community composition pointed out more into the direction of extensively farmed plots including crop yield (Yield), CEC, Pav, and concentrations of Mg, K and B. Thus, results indicate that extensive farming could have positive impact on the crop production, CEC and available P affecting via those also on symbiotrophic community. Variables that

explained the variation of the pathotrophic fungal community composition pointed out more towards organically farmed plots included sand content (SA) and the proportion of the second smallest soil aggregate size distribution class (Agsd_d), and those pointing out more towards conventionally farmed plots included crop yield (Yield), SI content, CEC, EC, Bs, TOC, OM, Nt, and concentrations of Cu, Ca, Mg and Mo.

In CS9, community composition of none of the three main functional guilds diverged between control and treatments, and none of the measured variables affected significantly the variation of the community composition of these guilds in the last monitoring year.

Figure 2.22. Two-dimensional non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) and principal-component (PCA) plots from CS6, CS7, CS8 and CS9 case studies showing the saprotrophic, pathotrophic and symbiotrophic fungal community composition with soil derived variables from the last monitoring years. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by farming practices (Treatment). Vectors represent significant soil derived variables ($p < 0.05$). See abbreviations in Figures 2.15.

In CS10a, PERMANOVA showed divergence in the community composition of pathotrophic fungi between treatments in the last monitoring year ($R^2=0.31$, $F=2.06$, $p=0.02$). Pairwise comparison could not verify these differences, but there was a trend towards greater divergence between control and plot with biostimulants (Biostim) ($p=0.1$). However, only one variable, particulate organic carbon (POC) content explained the variation of the pathotrophic community composition and pointed towards the control treatment (Figure 2.23). Even there was no divergence detected between saprotrophic and symbiotrophic community composition between treatments, some variables were significantly explaining their variation. For saprotrophs the variables included crop yield, Pav, EC, Nt and concentrations of K and B. For symbiotrips, crop yield and concentrations of Mn, Mg and B pointed out into opposite direction than other explaining variables including POC and contents of Si and Cl. In CS10b, PERMANOVA did not show divergence in the community composition of pathotrophic or symbiotrophic fungi between treatments in the last monitoring year. In turn, the community composition of saprotrophic fungi differed between treatments ($R^2=0.33$, $F=2.22$, $p=0.001$). Pairwise comparison could verify these differences between control and plots with both strip and broad undersowing treatment ($p=0.049$). However, none of the measured variables explained significantly the variation of the community composition in any of these three main guilds. In CS11, both saprotrophic and pathotrophic fungal community composition differed between treatments according to PERMANOVA (Sap, $R^2=0.32$, $F=2.11$, $p=0.002$; Pat, $R^2=0.38$, $F=2.77$, $p=0.001$; Sym, $R^2=0.42$, $F=3.28$, $p=0.01$). The difference between control and both diversification treatments was verified with pairwise comparison which showed rather equal difference between treatments for saprotrophs ($R^2=0.24$, $p=0.048$), bigger difference between control and diversified extensive farming for pathotrophs (DivExtWhe, $R^2=0.43$, $p=0.042$; ExtWhe, $R^2=0.31$, $p=0.042$), and hardly significant difference only between control and extensive farming ($R^2=0.49$, $p=0.05$) for symbiotrophs. Silt and sand content were the only significant variables explaining the variation in saprotrophs, and POC that of the variation in pathotrophs pointing to the direction of control plots.

Figure 2.23. Two-dimensional non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) and principal-component (PCA) plots from CS10a, CS10b and CS11 case studies showing the saprotrophic, pathotrophic and symbiotrophic fungal community composition with soil derived variables from the last monitoring years. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by farming practices (Treatment). Vectors represent significant soil derived variables ($p < 0.05$). See abbreviations in Figures 2.16.

In CS12, due to lack of replicates, the statistical power of the analysis is poor. Saprotrophic or symbiotrophic fungal community composition did not differ between treatments in the last monitoring year. However, the variation of saprotrophic community composition was explained by the concentration of Mn along the PC1 and other variables along PC2 axis including CEC, OM, TOC, Bs, and concentrations of Mg and Ca (Figu4e 2.24). In turn, PERMANOVA showed divergence in the community composition of pathotrophic fungi between treatments in the last monitoring year ($R^2 = 0.65$, $F = 1.83$, $p = 0.03$). Pairwise comparison could not verify these differences, but two variables, soil pH pointing out away from the treatment to the non-cultivated field edge and

concentration of Na were the only significant variables explaining the variation of the pathotrophic community composition.

Figure 2.24. Two-dimensional non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) and principal-component (PCA) plots from CS12 case study showing the saprotrophic, pathotrophic and symbiotrophic fungal community composition with soil derived variables from the last monitoring years. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by farming practices (Treatment). Vectors represent significant soil derived variables ($p < 0.05$). See abbreviations in Figure 2.17.

In CS13, none of the three functional fungal guild community compositions did differ between treatments in the last monitoring year. However, there were several variables that explained the variation of their community composition. For saprotrophs, explaining variables included TOC, OM, Nt and concentrations of Fe and B along the left side of the PC1 axis and starch concentration (STARCON), SA content, bulk density (BD) and the proportion of the second largest soil aggregate size distribution class (Agsd_c) in the opposite direction of the PC1 axis (Figure 2.25). For pathotrophs, explaining variables included SA content on the left side of the PC1 axis and several other variables pointing out to the opposite direction including EC, OM, Bs, Nt, N₂O gas, SI and CI contents, and concentrations of Fe, Mg, B and Ca. For symbiotrophs, starch content was pointing out to the right side of the PC1 and other significant variables including EC, CO₂ gas, POC and the proportion of the second smallest soil aggregate size distribution class (Agsd_d) in the opposite direction along PC1 axis. In CS14a, none of the three functional fungal guild community compositions did differ between treatments in the last monitoring year. However, there were several variables that explained the variation of their community composition. For saprotrophs, explaining variables included only crop yield along the NMDS2 axis and Mg concentration along the MDS1 axis. For pathotrophs, explaining variables included CH₄ gas along NMDS2 axis and other two Pav and Mg concentration along the other NMDS1 axis. For symbiotrophs, all three explaining variables pointed out to different directions in the ordination and they were POC, crop yield and the proportion of the largest soil aggregate size distribution class (Agsd_b). In CS14b, none of the three functional fungal guild community compositions did differ between treatments in the last monitoring year. However, there were a few variables that explained the variation of their community composition. For saprotrophs, explaining variables included K and POC along the first NMDS1 axis. For symbiotrophs, soil pH pointed out to the left side of the NMDS1 and Yield to the upper part of along the NMDS2 axis, whereas POC, Pav, K, Fe and Nt pointed out to the right side of NMDS1. In CS15, none of the three functional fungal guild community compositions did differ between treatments in the last monitoring year. However, there were several variables that explained the variation of their community composition. For

saprotrophs, explaining variables were scattered all over the ordination including Pav, water-holding capacity (WHC), EC, Bs, contents of SI, SA and CL, concentrations of Fe, Mn, Cu, Mg, Ca and B, and the proportion of the largest soil aggregate size distribution class (Agstd_b). For pathotrophs, there was only three variation explaining variables pointing into different directions, CEC, POC and concentration of Fe. For symbiotrophs, six explaining variables were pointing out to different directions in the ordination, NO₃ content to the upper left corner, CO₂ gas and concentrations to the upper right corner, and CL content and concentrations of Mg and B to the lower right corner of the ordination more towards the rye cover crop treatment.

Figure 2.25. Two-dimensional non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) and principal-component (PCA) plots from CS13, CS14a, CS14b and CS15 case studies showing the saprotrophic, pathotrophic and symbiotrophic fungal community composition with soil derived variables from the last monitoring years. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by farming practices (Treatment). Vectors represent significant soil derived variables ($p < 0.05$). See abbreviations in Figures 2.18.

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3 Microbial Biomass Characterization

3.1 Introduction

Over the past decades, European agriculture has been based mainly on conventional farming systems, characterized by monocultures, intensive mechanization, and excessive use of chemically synthesized fertilizers and pesticides. Although these practices have led to an increase in agricultural production, they have also led to soil and water degradation, increasing diseases and pests and reducing biodiversity, leading to a loss of long-term sustainability of farming systems (Morugan-Coronado et al., 2022; Tilman et al., 2002). Consequently, in Europe, agriculture has been considered one of the key areas for the ecological transition, with the “Farm to Fork” strategy being one of the fundamental pillars of the “European Green Deal”. This strategy aims to create a more sustainable food system with minimal environmental impact, as well as to guarantee the population's access to safe, nutritious, and affordable food (Farm to Fork Strategy, European Commission, 2023). In this sense, the implementation of green, conservationist, and appropriate agricultural practices and cropping systems can constitute a sustainable and viable alternative to reduce the pressure of current intensive agriculture, contributing to reducing soil degradation and improving its fertility, as well as increasing carbon sequestration and crop yield and quality (Scotti et al., 2015; Kraut-Cohen et al., 2020; Doran 2002). In this sense, soil microorganisms play a key role in important soil functions and services, including nutrient cycling, organic matter decomposition, soil aggregate stability, pollutant biodegradation, or climate regulation, among others. Due to these important functions and services, the activity of soil microbial communities determines the productivity and overall quality of terrestrial ecosystems (Montecchia et al., 2011). Therefore, maintaining or even increasing soil microbial abundance and diversity results essential to achieving more sustainable agricultural production (Morugan-Coronado et al., 2022; Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2016; FAO et al., 2020; Montecchia et al., 2011).

On the other hand, it is well known that certain agricultural practices can alter the chemical and physical properties of soils, leading to modifications of the microbial habitat and modifying soil quality, thus affecting microbial communities, and consequently, crop yield (Stagnari et al., 2014). However, these interrelationships between microbial communities, soil properties/ecosystem services, and agricultural production (crop yield and quality) have been little investigated.

The study of soil microbial abundance and the characterization of soil microbial communities are often carried out using the PLFA technique, which consists of extracting lipids from the cell membranes of microorganisms and using them as biomarkers, since they are only found in viable microbes. In this sense, changes in PLFA patterns are indicative of rapid changes in the microbial community structure. Furthermore, the total amount of PLFA is used to determine the total microbial biomass. Finally, it should be noted that specific PLFAs can also be used to determine the microbial biomass of different groups, such as bacterial PLFAs and fungal PLFAs (Bååth et al., 1992; Frostegård and Bååth, 1996; Frostegård et al., 1991; Morugan-Coronado et al., 2022).

Taking all this into account, in this report, the relationships between soil microbial abundance, crop yield and quality, and the provision of ecosystem services (e.g. greenhouse gas emissions, nutrient content, organic carbon content, soil pH, and other soil physicochemical properties) are investigated. These results are derived from WP5 case studies conducted in six different pedoclimatic regions in Europe. The results in this report correspond to the last sampling period and are presented separately for each case study.

3.2 Material and Methods

To estimate the abundance of different groups of microbes, the method described by Frostegård and Bååth (1996) was used. Briefly: lipids were extracted from soils using “Bligh and Dyer” solution, and then neutral lipids, glycolipids and phospholipids were separated using silica columns and solvents with different polarity: methanol for neutral lipids, acetone for glycolipids and chloroform for phospholipids. After separation, neutral lipids and phospholipids were subjected to mild alkaline methanolysis (transesterification) to break the lipids and obtain the fatty acids. After this step, the fatty acids were determined by gas chromatography. Different fatty acids are specific of different microbial groups, allowing to calculate the abundance of these groups by summing different fatty acids. Most of microbial groups were estimated using phospholipid fatty acids (PLFAs) while neutral lipid fatty acid (NLFA) 16:1 ω 5 was used to estimate the abundance of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (Table 3.1).

Relationships between soil physicochemical and environmental properties (listed Appendix Table 1.1), crop yield, and the abundance of the different microbial groups, were examined using Spearman’s rank correlations, with results visualized as heatmaps (Spearman, 1987). The statistical analyses were performed using R 4.4.1.

TABLE 3.1	
Total abundance	All determined PLFAs
Bacteria	PLFAs: i15:0, a15:0, 15:0, i16:0, 16:1 ω 9, 16:1 ω 7t, i17:0, a17:0, 17:0, cy17:0, 18:1 ω 7, cy19:0
Gram-positive Bacteria	PLFAs: br17:0, br18:0, i17:0, a17:0, i16:0, i16:1, 10Me16:0, 10Me17:0, i15:0, a15:0, 16:1 ω 9, 16:1 ω 7c, 18:1 ω 7 and 19:1
Gram-negative Bacteria	PLFAs: cy17:0, cy19:0, r-hydroxy fatty acids, 16:1 ω 9, 16:1 ω 7, 16:1 ω 5, 18:1 ω 7 and 19:1
Actinobacteria	PLFAs: 10Me16:0, 10Me17:0 and 10Me18:0
Fungi	PLFA: 18:2 ω 6 (linoleic acid)
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	NLFAs: 16:1 ω 5

Table 3.1. Fatty acid biomarkers used to estimate the abundance of different microbial groups.

3.3 Results and discussion

3.3.1 Relationship between soil properties and microbial abundance

Figures 3.1 to 3.17 show Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes and the different soil properties for each case study.

For CS1 (Mediterranean South region), the abundance of all studied microbial groups, both bacteria and fungi, was positively and significantly correlated with the exchangeable potassium (K_{ex}) content of the soils. Similarly, the soil total organic carbon (TOC) content was also positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of most microbial groups, except for Firmicutes bacteria and Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (Figure 3.1). On the other hand, the abundance of bacteria, except for Actinobacteria, was positively and significantly correlated with exchangeable cations content, such as Ca_{ex} and Mg_{ex} and, therefore, with the CEC and the sum of bases (Bs) (Figure 3.1). However, in the case of fungi, this correlation was only observed for Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi abundance. It is also worth noting that the abundances of Gram-negative bacteria and Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi were positively and significantly correlated with the available phosphorus (P_{av}) content of the soils. Finally, a positive and significant correlation was also observed between the abundance of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi and the available manganese content (Mn_{ba}) (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹) and the different soil properties for case study CS1 (Southern Mediterranean region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p-value<0.05; ** Significant at p-value<0.01.

For CS2 (Mediterranean South region), the abundance of all studied microbial groups was significantly and positively correlated with the total nitrogen (N_t) content of the soils, while it was significantly and negatively correlated with the exchangeable sodium (Na_{ex}) content. On the other hand, the abundance of most of the microbial groups here studied, except for Firmicutes bacteria, was significantly and positively correlated with the available phosphorus content (P_{ab}).

Figure 3.2. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹) and the different soil properties for case study CS2 (Southern Mediterranean region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p-value<0.05; ** Significant at p-value<0.01.

For CS3 (Lusitanian region), in general, with the exception of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi, the abundance of all studied microbial groups was positively and significantly correlated with soil organic matter-related parameters (OM, TOC, and Nt), as well as with exchange complex-related parameters (CEC, Ca_{ex} , Mg_{ex} , K_{ex} , and Bs), with the exception of exchangeable sodium (Na_{ex}) content, which did not show any relationship with the abundance of any microbial group. Other parameters that showed a positive and significant effect on the abundance of most microbial groups were $CaCO_3$ content, soil moisture content (FMA), available phosphorus content (P_{ab}), available iron content (Fe_{ab}), and available manganese content (Mn_{ab}). On the other hand, it was also observed that an increase in pH resulted in a lower abundance of Gram+ bacteria (Firmicutes and Actinobacteria), as well as Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi. However, it should be noted that, for CS3, the pH was very similar for the different soils here studied (pH in water varied between 4.6 and 5.1). Finally, it was also found that aggregates smaller than 53 μm favored the abundance of all groups of microorganisms, except for Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi, while aggregates with sizes between 250 and 2000 μm caused the opposite effect, that is, a decrease in the abundance of these microbial groups.

Figure 3.3. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes ($nmol\ PLFA\ g^{-1}$) and the different soil properties for case study CS3 (Lusitanian region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota

fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p -value <0.05 ; ** Significant at p -value <0.01 .

For CS4 (Lusitanian region) it was found that, in general, the abundance of the different microbial groups was positively and significantly correlated with the parameters related to the soil exchange complex (CEC, Ca_{ex} , Mg_{ex} , K_{ex} , Na_{ex} , and B_s), as well as with the available Cu, Zn, Mn, and B contents (Cu_{ab} , Zn_{ab} , Mn_{ab} , and B_{ab}). Finally, similarly to CS3, a higher content of aggregates between 53 and 250 μm resulted in a higher abundance of microorganisms, while a higher content of larger aggregates (250 – 2000 μm) resulted in a decrease in the abundance of microorganisms.

Figure 3.4. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g^{-1}) and the different soil properties for case study CS4 (Lusitanian region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p -value <0.05 ; ** Significant at p -value <0.01 .

For CS5, in general, as can be observed in Figure 3.5, a higher organic fraction content (OM, TOC, POC, and Nt) resulted in a higher abundance of the different microbial groups, except for Actinobacteria, whose abundance was not significantly correlated with any parameter related to soil organic fraction. In addition, a positive and significant correlation was also found between the total abundance of bacteria and Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi and the exchangeable magnesium (Mg_{ex}) content of the soils. Finally, a larger aggregate size resulted in a lower microbial abundance, especially for the Arbuscular mycorrhizal and Zygomycota fungi groups.

Figure 3.5. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g^{-1}) and the different soil properties for case study CS5 (Lusitanian region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unespecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.05$; ** Significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.01$.

For case study CS6 (Atlantic Central region), it was found that pH was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Actinobacteria (Gram+ bacteria), Gram- bacteria, and Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi. On the other hand, in this case study, the positive influence of organic matter on

the abundance of microorganisms was only observed for the Zygomycota fungi, whose abundance was positively and significantly correlated with the organic matter (OM) and total organic carbon (TOC) contents.

Regarding the soil exchange complex, it was found that the abundance of Actinobacteria (Gram+ bacteria) was positively and significantly correlated with the CEC, with the exchangeable calcium content (Ca_{ex}), and with the sum of bases (Bs), while the abundance of Zygomycota fungi was only significantly and positively correlated with the CEC. Finally, the abundance of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi was positively and significantly correlated with the exchangeable potassium content (K_{ex}). In contrast, exchangeable sodium (Na_{ex}) content was significantly and negatively correlated with the abundance of Firmicutes (Gram+ bacteria), Gram- bacteria, and Zygomycota fungi.

Regarding macronutrients, soil nitrate content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi, while available phosphorus (P_{ab}) content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Firmicutes (Gram+ bacteria), Gram- bacteria, and Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi.

Finally, certain micronutrients were also positively related to the abundance of certain groups of microorganisms. Thus, the available manganese content (Mn_{ab}) was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Firmicutes (Gram+ bacteria), and Zygomycota, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi, while the available copper (Cu_{ab}) and available zinc (Zn_{ab}) contents were positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Firmicutes (Gram+ bacteria).

Figure 3.6. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g^{-1}) and the different soil properties for case study CS6 (Atlantic Central region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p -value <0.05 ; ** Significant at p -value <0.01 .

For CS7 (Figure 3.7), it was observed that a higher bulk density resulted in a lower abundance of microorganisms, especially for Gram- bacteria, thus obtaining a significant and negative correlation between bulk density and the abundance of Gram- bacteria. On the other hand, an increase in the pH value resulted in an increase in the abundance of the different microbial groups, thus obtaining positive and significant correlations between the abundance of all the microorganism groups and pH values, except for Actinobacteria (Gram+ bacteria), whose abundance did not correlate significantly with pH. Similarly, an increase in electrical conductivity (EC) also resulted in an increase in the abundance of different groups of microorganisms. Thus, positive and significant correlations were obtained between EC and the abundance of Gram+ bacteria (Firmicutes and Actinobacteria), Zygomycota fungi, and unspecific microbials.

Regarding the organic fractions of soils, no significant correlation was observed between the abundance of microorganisms and the organic matter content. However, a significant and positive

correlation was obtained between total organic carbon (TOC) content and the abundance of Zygomycota fungi, as well as between particulate organic carbon (POC) and the abundance of Gram + bacteria (Firmicutes and Actinobacteria), Zygomycota fungi, and unspecific microbial. Total nitrogen (N_t) content was only significantly and positively correlated with the abundance of Actinobacteria (Gram + bacteria). Regarding the soil exchange complex, it was observed that the cation exchange capacity (CEC) and the sum of bases (Bs) were positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Firmicutes (Gram + bacteria), Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, Zygomycota fungi, unspecific microbials. In addition, in the case of Bs, a positive and significant correlation was also obtained with the abundance of Gram- bacteria. Thus, higher exchangeable base cation content resulted in a higher abundance of all microbial groups, except for Actinobacteria (Gram+ bacteria) and Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi, whose abundance was not significantly correlated with any parameter related to the soil exchange complex.

On the other hand, it was found that, in general, higher soil moisture resulted in higher abundance of microorganisms. In this sense, it was found that the current field moisture content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Firmicutes (Gram+ bacteria), Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, Zygomycota fungi, and unspecific microbial. Regarding macronutrients, available phosphorus (P_{ab}) content was found to be positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Gram+ bacteria (Firmicutes and Actinobacteria), Zygomycota fungi, and unspecific microbial, while it was not significantly related to the abundance of Gram- bacteria, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, and Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi. Finally, certain micronutrients such as Fe, Cu, Zn, and Mn, also favored the abundance of microorganisms, especially Zn, whose content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups here studied.

Figure 3.7. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹) and the different soil properties for case study CS7 (Atlantic Central region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p-value<0.05; ** Significant at p-value<0.01.

For case study CS8 (Figure 3.8), it was observed that higher soil bulk density resulted in lower microbial abundance. However, no significant correlations were found. Regarding soil organic fraction, total nitrogen (Nt) content was found to be positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi and Zygomycota fungi, while it was not significantly correlated with either Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi or any bacterial group. On the other hand, regarding the soil exchange complex, Mg_{ex} content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups here studied, while K_{ex} content was also positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microorganism groups, except with the abundance of Actinobacteria and Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi. Finally, regarding macronutrients, it was found that the available phosphorus (P_{av}) content was correlated with the abundance of all the

microbial groups here studied, indicating that the soils with a higher P_{av} content were those that presented a higher microbial abundance.

Figure 3.8. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g^{-1}) and the different soil properties for case study CS8 (Atlantic Central region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p -value <0.05 ; ** Significant at p -value <0.01 .

For case study CS9 (Figure 3.9), it was observed that neither pH nor soil organic matter content showed any significant effect on the abundance of microorganisms. However, it was found that electrical conductivity (EC) was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Gram+ bacteria (Actinobacteria and Firmicutes), with the abundance of Gram- bacteria, and with the abundance of Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi. Regarding the soil exchange complex, it was found that the Na_{ex} content was significantly and positively correlated with the abundance of Gram- bacteria.

On the other hand, the actual field moisture content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups here studied, clearly indicating that a higher soil moisture content leads to a higher microbial abundance. Finally, it was also found that the bioavailable Cu and Zn content led to a decrease in the abundance of certain groups of microorganisms. In this sense, the available Cu content was significantly and negatively correlated with the abundance of Firmicutes (Gram+ bacteria) and with the abundance of Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, while the available Zn content was significantly and negatively correlated with the abundance of Gram- bacteria and with the abundance of Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi.

Figure 3.9. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g^{-1}) and the different soil properties for case study CS9 (Atlantic Central region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p -value <0.05 ; ** Significant at p -value <0.01 .

For case study C10a (Figure 3.10), it was observed that soils with a higher pH and electrical conductivity (EC) were those that presented a greater abundance of microorganisms. Thus, it was obtained that pH, as well as EC, were positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all the microbial groups here studied, with the exception of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi, whose abundance was not significantly correlated with either pH or EC. Regarding soil organic fraction, it was obtained that the total nitrogen (Nt) content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Actinobacteria (Gram+ bacteria), Gram- bacteria, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, Zygomycota fungi, and unspecific microbial, while no significant correlation was observed with the abundance of Firmicutes bacteria or Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi. Similarly, both CEC and sum of bases (Bs) were positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups here studied, except with Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi, whose abundance did not show any significant correlation with any parameter related to the soil exchange complex. It should also be noted that Ca_{ex} and Mg_{ex} were the exchange cations that had a greater effect on the abundance of the different microbial groups, while K_{ex} content was only positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Actinobacteria (Gram+ bacteria), whereas Na_{ex} content did not show any significant relationship with the abundance of any microbial group. Similarly to what was observed for the parameters related to the soil exchange complex, the $CaCO_3$ content was also positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups here studied, except for Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi.

Contrary to what was observed for other case studies, where the soil moisture content favored the abundance of most of the groups of microorganisms studied here, for CS10a, the soil moisture content was only positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Firmicutes (Gram+ bacteria), total fungi, and unspecific fungi.

On the other hand, the soil nitrate content (NO_3) was significantly and negatively correlated with the abundance of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi, indicating that the richest soils in nitrates were those that presented a lower abundance of this group of microbes. Regarding micronutrients, it was found that the available iron (Fe_{av}) content exhibited a negative effect on the abundance of most of the microbial groups here studied, correlating negatively and significantly with the abundance of all microbial groups, except for Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi. Similarly, available copper (Cu_{av}) content was also significantly and negatively correlated with the abundance of Gram- bacteria, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, and Zygomycota fungi.

Finally, soil aggregate size distribution also had a significant effect on microorganism abundance. Thus, soils with a higher content of aggregates larger than 2000 μm were those with a higher abundance of Firmicutes (Gram+ bacteria), Gram- bacteria, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, Zygomycota fungi, and unspecific microbial, while soils with a higher content of aggregates between 53 and 250 μm were those with a lower abundance of all microbial groups, except for Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi, whose abundance was not related to soil aggregate distribution.

Figure 3.10. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g^{-1}) and the different soil properties for case study CS10a (Continental region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p -value <0.05 ; ** Significant at p -value <0.01 .

For case study 10b (Figure 3.11), no significant relationship was observed between microbial abundance and soil bulk density, pH, or electrical conductivity. Regarding soil organic fraction, total organic carbon (TOC) content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, while total nitrogen (Nt) content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Gram- bacteria and unspecific microbial. Regarding parameters related to the soil exchange complex, only exchangeable potassium (K_{ex}) content was found to be positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, while none of the other parameters (CEC, Bs, Ca_{ex} , Mg_{ex} , and Na_{ex}) was found to be significantly correlated with the abundance of any microbial group.

On the other hand, a significant and negative correlation was found between soil CaCO_3 content and the abundance of Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi. Regarding soil moisture, contrary to other case studies, for CS10b, it was observed that the soil moisture content was significantly and negatively correlated with the abundance of the three groups of fungi studied here. Finally, it was also found that the available copper (Cu_{av}) content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Zygomycota fungi and unspecific microbial, while Mn_{av} was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Actinobacteria (Gram+ bacteria).

Figure 3.11. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g^{-1}) and the different soil properties for case study CS10b (Continental region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.05$; ** Significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.01$.

For CS11 (Figure 3.12), the abundance of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi and of unspecific microbial was found to be positively and significantly correlated with soil pH, indicating that an increase in soil pH resulted in a higher abundance of these microbial groups. In addition, it was also

found that electrical conductivity (EC) was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi.

Regarding the parameters related to the soil organic fraction, it was found that both the organic matter (OM) content and the total nitrogen (Nt) content were positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups, except for Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi, while the total soil organic carbon (TOC) content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Gram+ and Gram- bacteria (and, therefore, with the total abundance of bacteria), and with the abundance of Zygomycota fungi. Similar, regarding the soil exchange complex, K_{ex} content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups here studied, while CEC, Ca_{ex} , and Na_{ex} were also positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups, except for the abundance of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi. However, Mg_{ex} content was only positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi and with the abundance of unspecific microbial, while the sum of bases (Bs) was only positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, Zygomycota fungi and unspecific microbial.

On the other hand, soil moisture content was only positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, while nitrate (NO_3) content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Firmicutes bacteria and Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi. On the contrary, Fe_{av} content was negatively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups here studied, except for Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi, while Zn_{av} content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi and Zygomycota fungi.

Finally, it was also observed that soils with a higher content of aggregates larger than 2000 μm were those that presented a lower abundance of microorganisms.

Figure 3.12. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g^{-1}) and the different soil properties for case study CS11 (Continental region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p -value <0.05 ; ** Significant at p -value <0.01 .

For CS12 (Figure 3.13), in general, the soil organic fraction was the one that determined the abundance of microorganisms. Thus, the contents of organic matter (OM), total organic carbon (TOC) and total nitrogen (Nt) were positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Firmicutes (Gram+ bacteria), while the content of particulate organic carbon (POC) was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Gram+ bacteria (Firmicutes and Actinobacteria) and with the abundance of Zygomycota fungi. Finally, it should also be noted that the available manganese (Mn_{av}) content was significantly and positively correlated with the abundance of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi.

Figure 3.13. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹) and the different soil properties for case study CS12 (Nemoral region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p-value<0.05; ** Significant at p-value<0.01.

For CS13 (Figure 3.14), it was found that nitrous oxide (NO₂) concentration was significantly and positively correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups, while carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of the different bacterial groups here studied, as well as with the abundance of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi and unspecific microbial. On the contrary, methane (CH₄) concentration was negatively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi.

On the other hand, bulk density was negatively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups. Similarly, it was also observed that, in general, an increase in soil pH resulted in a decrease in microbial abundance. On the contrary, electrical conductivity (EC) was found to be positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups, except for the abundance of Ascomycete and Basidiomycete microbials. Regarding the soil organic fraction, organic

matter (OM) content, total organic carbon (TOC) content, and total nitrogen (Nt) content, were positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups here studied, except for Ascomycete and Basidiomycete microbials, whose abundance was not significantly correlated with TOC content. Furthermore, particulate organic carbon (POC) content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of bacteria, both Gram+ and Gram-, as well as with the abundance of Ascomycete and Basidiomycete fungi and unspecific microbial. Similarly, all parameters related to the soil exchange complex (CEC, Ca_{ex} , Mg_{ex} , K_{ex} , Na_{ex} , and Na_{ex}), as well as $CaCO_3$ and moisture contents, were positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups, except for Ascomycete and Basidiomycete fungi, whose abundance was not correlated with any of these parameters. On the other hand, nitrate content (NO_3) content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of both Gram+ and Gram- bacteria, as well as with the abundance of unspecific microbial.

Regarding micronutrients, Fe_{av} content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups, whereas Cu_{av} content was positively and significantly correlated only with the abundance of Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi. On the contrary, Zn_{av} content was significantly and negatively correlated with the abundance of both Gram+ and Gram- bacteria, with the abundance of Zygomycota fungi, and with the abundance of unspecific microbial, whereas Mo_{av} content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of both Gram+ and Gram- bacteria, with the abundance of Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, and with the abundance of unspecific microbial. Finally, it was also observed that soils with a greater abundance of smaller aggregates were those that presented a greater microbial abundance.

Figure 3.14. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹) and the different soil properties for case study CS13 (Boreal region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p-value<0.05; ** Significant at p-value<0.01.

For CS14a (Figure 3.15), the abundance of unspecific microbials was found to be significantly and negatively correlated with soil pH, while the abundance of the other microbial groups did not show any significant relationship with pH. Regarding the soil organic fraction, both the organic matter (OM) content and the total nitrogen (Nt) content were positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Gram+ bacteria (Firmicutes and Actinobacteria), Gram- bacteria, and unspecific microbial. In addition, the soil organic matter (OM) content was also positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Zygomycota fungi.

Regarding the soil exchange complex, the Mg_{ex}, K_{ex}, and Na_{ex} contents were positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Firmicutes (Gram+ bacteria) and unspecific microbial. In addition, Mg_{ex} content was also positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Actinobacteria (Gram+ bacteria), while K_{ex} and Na_{ex} contents were also positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Gram- bacteria.

On the other hand, soil CaCO₃ content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Firmicutes (Gram+ bacteria), Gram- bacteria, and unspecific microbial, while soil moisture was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Gram+ bacteria (Firmicutes and Actinobacteria) and with the abundance of unspecific microbial.

Finally, both available phosphorus (P_{av}) and available iron (Fe_{av}) contents were positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of unspecific microbial.

Figure 3.15. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹) and the different soil properties for case study CS14a (Boreal region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p-value<0.05; ** Significant at p-value<0.01.

For CS14b (Figure 3.16), it was found that EC was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi. Regarding the soil organic fraction, it was found that the organic matter (OM) content and the total nitrogen (Nt) content were positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all the microbial groups here studied, except for Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi, whose abundance was not correlated with any parameter

related to the soil organic fraction. In addition, a positive and significant correlation was also found between the total organic carbon (TOC) content and the abundance of Gram- bacteria. Regarding the soil exchange complex, only K_{ex} content was found to be positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Actinobacteria (Gram+ bacteria).

On the other hand, it was found that the NH_4 content was significantly and negatively correlated with the abundance of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi, while the nitrate (NO_3) content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Gram+ bacteria (Firmicutes and Actinobacteria), Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, and unspecific microbial. Finally, regarding micronutrients, it was found that the available manganese (Mn_{av}) content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all the microbial groups here studied, except for Actinobacteria, whose abundance was not related to the soil manganese content.

Figure 3.16. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g^{-1}) and the different soil properties for case study CS14b (Boreal region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p -value <0.05 ; ** Significant at p -value <0.01 .

For CS15 (Figure 3.17), neither the concentration of any of the gases studied, nor the soil pH, nor the parameters related to the soil exchange complex, had a significant effect on the abundance of microorganisms. However, other parameters, such as conductivity, parameters related to the soil organic fraction, the content of certain micronutrients, and the soil aggregates distribution, showed significant effects on the abundance of certain groups of microorganisms. In this sense, the electrical conductivity (EC) was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Actinobacteria (Gram+ bacteria), Gram- bacteria, and Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi. Regarding the soil organic fraction, the organic matter (OM) content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Actinobacteria (Gram+ bacteria) and Gram- bacteria, while the total organic carbon (TOC) content was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Actinobacteria (Gram+ bacteria) and Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi. Regarding total nitrogen (Nt) content, this was only positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi.

On the other hand, regarding micronutrient content, Fe_{av} was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Actinobacteria (Gram+ bacteria), Gram- bacteria, and unspecific microbial, while Mn_{av} was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Actinobacteria (Gram+ bacteria), Gram- bacteria, and Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi. Finally, regarding soil aggregate distribution, it was found that aggregates between 250 and 2000 µm favored the abundance of microorganisms, while aggregates smaller than 53 µm resulted in a lower abundance of microorganisms.

Figure 3.17. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g^{-1}) and the different soil properties for case study CS15 (Boreal region). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p -value <0.05 ; ** Significant at p -value <0.01 .

3.3.2 Relationship between soil properties and crop yield

Figures 3.18 to 3.29 show Spearman's correlations between the abundance of different groups of microbes and the crop yield for each case study.

For CS1 (Figure 3.18), it was found that crop yield was only positively and significantly correlated with the content of aggregates with size between 53 and 250 μm , indicating that soils with a higher percentage of this aggregate were those that presented a higher crop yield. Regarding the other parameters related to crop yield, it was found that tuber weight was positively and significantly correlated with soil moisture, while it was also negatively and significantly correlated with pH.

On the other hand, the tuber size distribution was positively and significantly correlated with soil moisture, with Cu_{av} content and with sand content, while it was significantly and negatively correlated with pH. Finally, starch content was significantly and negatively correlated with the content of certain micronutrients (such as P_{av} , Fe_{av} , and Mn_{av}), as well as with K_{ex} .

Figure 3.18. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between parameters related to crop yield and the different soil properties for case study CS1 (Mediterranean Soth region). Abbreviations: YIELD, crop yield (kg ha^{-1}); FWEIG, tuber weight (g); FTDISTRIB, tuber size distribution (V); STARCON, starch content (%). Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.05$; ** Significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.01$.

For CS2 (Figure 3.19), it was found that crop yield was negatively and significantly correlated with pH and total soil organic carbon (TOC), while the moisture content of grains was significantly and negatively correlated with the content of Fe_{av} and Mn_{av} .

Figure 3.19. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between parameters related to crop yield and the different soil properties for case study CS2 (Mediterranean Soth region). Abbreviations: YIELD, crop yield (kg ha^{-1}); GRMOIST, moisture content of grains (%). Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.05$; ** Significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.01$.

For CS3, CS4, and CS5, no significant correlation was found between parameters related to crop yield and soil properties. However, for CS6 (Figure 3.20), crop yield was positively and significantly correlated with soil pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total organic carbon (TOC) content, nitrate (NO_3) content, and Mg_{ex} and K_{ex} contents. On the contrary, crop yield was negatively and significantly correlated with Fe_{av} content.

Figure 3.20. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between parameters related to crop yield and the different soil properties for case study CS6 (Atlantic Central region). Abbreviations: YIELD, crop yield (kg ha⁻¹). Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p-value<0.05; ** Significant at p-value<0.01.

For CS7 no significant correlation was found between parameters related to crop yield and soil properties.

On the other hand, similarly to what was observed for CS6, for CS8 (Figure 3.21) both the crop yield and the tuber weight were positively and significantly correlated with pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total nitrogen (Nt) content, nitrate (NO₃) content, P_{av} content, and Mg_{ex} and K_{ex} contents and, therefore, with the CEC and with the sum of bases (Bs).

Figure 3.21. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between parameters related to crop yield and the different soil properties for case study CS8 (Atlantic Central region). Abbreviations: YIELD, crop yield (kg ha⁻¹); FWEIG, tuber weight (g). Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p-value<0.05; ** Significant at p-value<0.01.

For CS9 (Figure 3.22), the crop yield was only positively and significantly correlated with the exchangeable sodium content (Na_{ex}).

Figure 3.22. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between parameters related to crop yield and the different soil properties for case study CS9 (Atlantic Central region). Abbreviations: YIELD, crop yield (kg ha^{-1}). Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.05$; ** Significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.01$.

For CS10a (Figure 3.23), crop yield was positively and significantly correlated with pH, EC, Mg_{ex} content (and therefore CEC and sum of bases), CaCO_3 content, nitrate (NO_3) content, and Mn_{av} content, while it was negatively and significantly correlated with Fe_{av} content.

On the other hand, moisture content of grains was only significantly correlated with bulk density, indicating that soils with higher density are those that result in a higher grain moisture content.

Figure 3.23. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between parameters related to crop yield and the different soil properties for case study CS10a (Continental region). Abbreviations: YIELD, crop yield (kg ha⁻¹); GRMOIST, moisture content of grains (%). Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p-value<0.05; ** Significant at p-value<0.01.

For CS10b no significant correlation was found between parameters related to crop yield and soil properties, while for CS11 (Figure 3.24) it was observed that the crop yield was positively and significantly correlated with soil moisture, indicating that soils with a higher moisture content were those that gave rise to a higher crop yield.

Figure 3.24. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between parameters related to crop yield and the different soil properties for case study CS11 (Continental region). Abbreviations: YIELD, crop yield (kg ha⁻¹); GRPROT, protein content of grains (%). Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p-value<0.05; ** Significant at p-value<0.01.

For CS12 (Figure 3.25), it was found that crop yield was significantly and positively correlated with Na_{ex} content. On the contrary, it was significantly and negatively correlated with CaCO_3 content and with electrical conductivity (EC).

Figure 3.25. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between parameters related to crop yield and the different soil properties for case study CS12 (Nemoral region). Abbreviations: YIELD, crop yield (kg ha^{-1}). Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.05$; ** Significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.01$.

For CS13 (Figure 3.26), it was obtained that crop yield was positively and significantly correlated with pH, indicating that soils with higher pH had a higher crop yield. On the other hand, it was also obtained that starch content was positively and significantly correlated with bulk density and pH, while it was negatively and significantly correlated with parameters related to the soil organic fraction (OM, TOC, and POC). Finally, it was also obtained that soils with a higher proportion of aggregates larger than $2000 \mu\text{m}$ were those that gave rise to a higher starch content, while soils with a higher proportion of aggregates between 53 and $250 \mu\text{m}$ were those that gave rise to a lower starch content.

Figure 3.26. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between parameters related to crop yield and the different soil properties for case study CS13 (Boreal region). Abbreviations: YIELD, crop yield (kg ha^{-1}); STARCON, starch content (g). Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.05$; ** Significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.01$.

For CS14a (Figure 3.274), crop yield was positively and significantly correlated with soil pH, as well as with available Cu and Zn contents. At the same time, crop yield was also negatively and significantly correlated with total nitrogen (Nt) content, as well as with available phosphorus (P_{av}) and iron (Fe_{av}) contents.

Figure 3.27. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between parameters related to crop yield and the different soil properties for case study CS14a (Boreal region). Abbreviations: YIELD, crop yield (kg ha^{-1}). Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.05$; ** Significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.01$.

For CS14b (Figure 3.28) only a significant and negative correlation between crop yield and available phosphorus (P_{av}) content was found, indicating that soils with a higher content P_{av} were those that presented a lower crop yield.

Figure 3.28. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between parameters related to crop yield and the different soil properties for case study CS14b (Boreal region). Abbreviations: YIELD, crop yield (kg ha⁻¹). Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p-value<0.05; ** Significant at p-value<0.01.

For CS15 (Figure 3.29), crop yield was positively and significantly correlated with total organic carbon (TOC) and total nitrogen (Nt) contents, as well as with Mg_{ex} and Ca_{ex} contents. In addition, a positive and significant relationship was also found between crop yield and available molybdenum (Mo_{av}) content.

On the other hand, starch content was positively and significantly correlated with the content of aggregates with a size between 250 and 2000 µm.

Figure 3.29. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between parameters related to crop yield and the different soil properties for case study CS15 (Boreal region). Abbreviations: YIELD, crop yield (kg ha⁻¹); STARCON, starch content (g). Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p-value<0.05; ** Significant at p-value<0.01.

3.3.3 Relationship between crop yield and microbial abundance

Significant relationships between yield and microbial abundance were only found for CS7, CS8, CS10a, and CS13.

For CS7 (Figure 3.30), it was obtained that crop yield was not correlated with the abundance of any microbial group. However, it was found that the abundance of Actinobacteria was significantly and negatively correlated with the starch content.

Figure 3.30. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between parameters related to crop yield and the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g^{-1}) for case study CS7 (Atlantic Central region). Abbreviations: YIELD, crop yield ($kg\ ha^{-1}$); STARCON, starch content (g). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G-bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p -value <0.05 ; ** Significant at p -value <0.01 .

On the other hand, for CS8 (Figure 3.31), it was found that the crop yield was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups. Similarly, it was also found that the tuber weight was also positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of all microbial groups, except for the abundance of Actinobacteria (Gram+ bacteria). Therefore, from these results, it can be stated that in CS8, a higher abundance of microorganisms leads to a higher crop yield.

Figure 3.31. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between parameters related to crop yield and the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g^{-1}) for case study CS8 (Atlantic Central region). Abbreviations: YIELD, crop yield ($kg\ ha^{-1}$); FWEIG, tuber weight (g). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p -value <0.05 ; ** Significant at p -value <0.01 .

Similarly, for CS10a (Figure 3.32) it was also found that crop yield was positively and significantly correlated with the abundance of most microbial groups, except for Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi, which did not show any significant correlation with crop yield.

Figure 3.32. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between parameters related to crop yield and the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g^{-1}) for case study CS10a (Continental region). Abbreviations: YIELD, crop yield ($kg\ ha^{-1}$); GRMOIST, moisture content of grains (%). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p -value <0.05 ; ** Significant at p -value <0.01 .

Finally, for CS13 (Figure 3.33), it was found that starch content was negatively and significantly correlated with the abundance of Gram+ bacteria (Firmicutes and Actinobacteria), Gram- bacteria, Zygomycota fungi and unspecific microbial.

Figure 3.33. Heatmap representing Spearman's correlations between parameters related to crop yield and the abundance of different groups of microbes (nmol PLFA g⁻¹) for case study CS13 (Boreal region). Abbreviations: YIELD, crop yield (kg ha⁻¹); STARCON, starch content (%). Abbreviations: FIR, Firmicutes; ACTI, Actinobacteria; G Positive, Gram+ bacteria; G Negative, G- bacteria; BACT, Total bacteria; AMF, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; ZYGO, Zygomycota fungi; ASCO/BASI, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi; Uns MICRO, Unspecific microbial; TtPLFA, Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs. Abbreviations of soil properties are found in Appendix Table 1.1. *Significant at p-value<0.05; ** Significant at p-value<0.01.

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4 Nematode diversity

4.1 Introduction

Soils are fundamental to the functioning of ecosystems such as plant growth, regulating water flow, cycling nutrients, hosting a vast array of biodiversity and global climate stability (Ial, 2004; Telo da Gama, 2023). As a consequence, their physical, chemical, and biological properties directly influence the ecosystem services they provide.

In this chapter we focus on nematode communities as part of the soil biodiversity. Nematode communities are excellent bioindicators of soil health due to their sensitivity to changes in soil conditions, such as nutrient availability, organic matter content, and pH (Ferris et al., 2001). This causes the assessment of nematode communities in agricultural soils to be helpful for understanding soil health condition, diagnosing potential crop issues, and guiding sustainable agricultural management practices (Lazarova et al., 2021; Melakenerhan et al., 2021), as well as climate change in general (Pires et al., 2023).

The nematode communities are related to the physical and chemical soil properties collected from WP5 case studies conducted across six European regions. Data is divided separately for each case study to provide detailed insights. As soil properties are linked to ecosystem services, as mentioned before, this analysis will deliver data to understand the relationship between nematode communities and ecosystem services. Ecosystem services analyzed include greenhouse gas emissions, soil carbon content, nutrient levels, etc. The outcome itself will further be discussed in Deliverable Report 5.4.

4.2 Material and Methods

4.2.1 Soil nematode extraction

From a total of 17 case-studies with a variety of agricultural practices, localized in 9 different pedoclimatic regions, soil samples were collected and their physical, chemical, and biological properties measured. More information about the case-studies, their set-up, management and location, can be found in Deliverable Report D5.4. The physical and chemical properties measured can be found in the tabel in chapter Annexes. The nematode extraction was conducted as explained in Deliverable Report 5.2.

4.2.2 Nematode community sequencing and analysis

All nematode samples were analyzed molecularly by DNA-metabarcoding as explained in Deliverable Report D5.2. A more detailed description can be found in the Handbook of WP3 ('Protocols for sampling, general soil characterization and soil biodiversity analysis', (Calviño et al., 2020; <http://soildiveragro.eu/publications/books/>) and the Deliverable report D3.3. Bioinformatics for the nematode 18S rRNA gene sequence data was conducted using the DADA2 pipeline (Callahan et al., 2016), further analysis comprised several packages applied in the open-source programming language and software environment 'R' version 4.4.1 (R Core Team, 2024) as described also in the previously published D5.2 report. Additionally, soil physiochemical parameters (data available in Annexes) were used to investigate their effects on the variation in nematode ASV composition using the *envfit* function of the *vegan* package. Only those soil physiochemical parameters being significantly ($p < 0.005$) associated with the nematode community composition were included in the NMDS plots. Significance is determined by comparing the observed fit against randomized data through permutation testing. The arrows of the vectors represent the direction of the correlation for the variables, the lengths indicate the strength of the relationship (the longer, the stronger the relationships; data points that are closer to the arrow indicate that they are associated with higher values of the environmental variable).

4.3 Results and discussion

4.3.1 Interrelationship between soil ecosystem services and beta diversity

Case-studies 1 & 2, Mediterranean South region

In table 4.1 can be seen that from the 34, in case of CS1, and 30 physical and chemical parameters, in case of CS2, 17 are significantly shaping the nematode communities ($p < 0.005$). The parameters are not the same for both case-studies. Only pHKCl, POC, Mg, K, Pav, Cu, Zn, Mn and Agsd_c affect the nematode communities in both case-studies when considering the soil samples from the start (2021) and the end (2023 for CS1 and 2022 for CS2) of the experiment.

TABLE 4.1

	CS1	CS2	CS3	CS4	CS5	CS6	CS7	CS8	CS9
CH4	0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CO2	0,007	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
N2O	0,137	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

BD	0,01	-	-	-	-	0,659	0,001	0,026	-
SA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SI	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
MDS	0,3	0,001	0,031	0,089	0,300	0,001	0,031	0,001	0,001
pH	0,509	0,042	0,476	0,001	0,007	0,001	0,096	0,072	0,234
pHKC I	0,004	0,001	0,231	0,594	0,073	0,001	0,180	0,233	0,241
pHCa Cl	0,001	0,140	0,642	0,001	0,030	0,001	0,938	0,010	0,017
EC	0,001	0,018	0,004	0,001	0,315	0,001	0,486	0,103	0,057
OM	0,997	0,105	0,052	0,002	0,563	0,003	0,001	0,001	0,009
TOC	0,306	0,159	0,268	0,012	0,447	0,001	0,623	0,001	0,629
POC	0,001	0,001	0,002	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,017	0,001	0,002
Nt	0,001	0,472	0,255	0,027	0,601	0,338	0,117	0,001	0,013
CEC	0,001	0,881	0,003	0,012	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
Ca	0,001	0,982	0,230	0,001	0,410	0,001	0,001	0,004	0,001
Mg	0,001	0,001	0,288	0,001	0,316	0,001	0,001	0,122	0,001
K	0,003	0,001	0,246	0,166	0,575	0,001	0,052	0,062	0,001
Na	0,434	0,001	0,029	0,022	0,030	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
Bs	0,001	0,650	0,295	0,001	0,233	0,221	0,001	0,017	0,007
CaCO 3	0,264	0,854	0,687	0,003	0,003	0,324	0,361	0,605	0,004
FM	0,043	0,001	0,081	0,114	0,160	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,224
NH4	0,039	0,001	0,071	0,009	0,028	0,001	0,001	0,003	0,001
NO3	0,013	0,001	0,911	0,001	0,003	0,001	0,001	0,119	0,003
Pav	0,001	0,001	0,023	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,004
Fe	0,001	0,020	0,001						
Cu	0,001	0,001	0,079	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
Zn	0,001	0,001	0,009	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
Mn	0,001	0,001	0,004	0,001	0,005	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
Mo	0,164	0,073	0,001						
Bba	0,351	0,001	1,000	0,012	0,018	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
Agsd _b	0,103	0,875	0,078	0,132	0,067	0,097	0,090	0,367	0,138
Agsd _c	0,003	0,003	0,073	0,005	0,004	0,115	0,035	0,001	0,085
Agsd _d	0,218	0,003	0,149	0,139	0,416	0,668	0,715	0,001	0,572
Agsd _e	0,011	0,002	0,223	0,007	0,001	0,396	0,004	0,006	0,902

Table 4.1. P-values of the listed parameters for case studies (CS) 1 till 9 analysed by the *envfit* program in R. P-values (p) less than or equal to 0.005 (in red) are considered statically significant. Explanantion of the physical and chemical properties applied can be found in the tabel in chapter Annexes.

Figure 4.1. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 1 and 2. The vectors are limited to those physical and chemical parameters that significantly shaped the nematode communities (see Table 4.1). Case-study 1: a = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced chemical fertilizer, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% chemical fertilizer. Case-study 2: a = reduced organic fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced organic fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced organic, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% organic fertilizer. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments, a different symbol (shape) is used for the sampling events.

The vectors in figure 4.1 are more or less directed to the left or the right. It means that they differently influence the nematode communities, being it positively or negatively, depending on the position of the data points. Clearly, the data points from both sampling events are separated and different parameters influenced the nematode communities depending on the year of sampling. No clear relationships concerning parameters shaping the nematode communities from a certain treatment conducted on the case-study can be noticed as the datapoint are scattered on the NMDS plot. Only in case-study 2, Pav and POC seem to influence the nematode communities of treatments “a” and “c”, while Agsd_e and Mg tend to shape the other two treatments (“b” and “Ctrl”).

Case-studies 3, 4 & 5, Lusitanian region

For case-studies 3 till 5, 30 physical and chemical parameters are listed in Table 4.1. Only 6 parameters measured for casestudy 3 are significantly shaping the nematode communities when considering the soil samples from the start (2021) and the end (2023) of the experiment. For case-studies 4 and 5 (same years), it concerns 17 and 11 parameters respectively. The parameters POC, Fe, Mn and Mo are influencing the nematode communities for all the three case-studies together.

Figure 4.2. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 3, 4 and 5. The vectors are limited to those physical and chemical parameters that significantly shaped the nematode communities (see Table 4.1). Case-study 3: a = alternative crop rotation 1, b = alternative crop rotation 2, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional crop rotation. Case-study 4: a = mycorrhiza + reduced P fertilization, b = mycorrhiza and no P fertilization, c = reduced P fertilization, d = no P fertilization, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional P fertilization. Case-study 5: a = conventional fungicide application, b = no fungicide application, Ctrl = control treatment = pest alert system. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments, a different symbol is used for the sampling events.

The vectors in figure 4.2 are again more or less grouped, directed opposite each other. It means that both groups of parameters influence the nematode communities differently depending on the position of the data points. The data points of case-studies 4 and 5 are clearly separated depending on the year of sampling. The same is true for case-study 3 although less obvious. Different parameters influenced the nematode communities depending on the year of sampling. No clear relationships concerning parameters shaping the nematode communities from a certain treatment conducted on the case-study can be noticed as the datapoint are scattered on the NMDS plot.

Case-studies 6 till 9, Atlantic Central region

For case-studies 6 till 8, thirty-one, for case-study 9, thirty physical and chemical parameters are listed in Table 4.1. Most parameters did significantly shape the nematode community compositions. Only 8, 13, 12 and 13 parameters measured in case-study 6 till 9 respectively, are not significantly shaping the nematode communities. Ten parameters are shaping the nematode communities in all case-studies of the Atlantic Central region (Table 4.1).

Figure 4.3. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 6 till 9. The vectors are limited to those physical and chemical parameters that significantly shaped the nematode communities (see Table 4.1). Case-study 6: a = cover crop mowed and removed, b = plus farm yard manure, c = cover crop mowed and removed plus farm yard manure, d = plus farm yard manure co-composted with straw, e = cover crop mowed and removed plus farm yard manure co-composted with straw, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 7: a = Phacelia/Egyptian clover cover crop mixture, b = 5-species cover crop mixture, c = 12-species cover crop mixture, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 8: a = conventional extensive farming system, b = organic intensive farming system, c = organic extensive farming system, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional intensive farming system. Case-study 9: a = compost, b = farm yard manure, c = silage grass, Ctrl = control treatment = no fertilizer. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments, a different symbol is used for the sampling events. Insufficient number of repeats in CS9 made it impossible to draw the NMDS plot.

TABLE 4.2							
CS10a	CS10b	CS11	CS12	CS13	CS14a	CS14b	CS15

CH4	-	-	-	-	0,597	0,209	0,745	0,119
CO2	-	-	-	-	0,195	0,130	0,009	0,747
N2O	-	-	-	-	0,424	0,235	0,014	0,3
BD	0,001	0,035	0,037	0,594	-	-	0,203	-
SA	-	-	-	-	-	0,147	0,55	0,945
SI	-	-	-	-	-	0,879	0,194	0,759
CL	-	-	-	-	-	0,261	0,05	0,9
MDS	0,212	0,004	0,001	0,017	0,090	0,188	0,035	0,329
pH	0,356	0,001	0,002	0,019	0,004	0,445	0,005	0,543
pHKCl	0,425	0,001	0,016	0,038	0,001	0,001	0,292	0,084
pHCaCl	0,044	0,001	0,051	0,028	0,452	0,001	0,117	0,389
EC	0,511	0,001	0,003	0,078	0,194	0,001	0,106	0,266
OM	0,014	0,051	0,310	0,372	0,213	0,202	0,16	0,28
TOC	0,107	0,007	0,405	0,323	0,184	0,772	0,425	0,273
POC	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,038	0,057	0,002	0,001	0,001
Nt	0,775	0,286	0,496	0,237	0,086	0,107	0,124	0,185
CEC	0,449	0,005	0,001	0,093	0,004	0,068	0,001	0,199
Ca	0,323	0,004	0,061	0,058	0,042	0,696	0,204	0,196
Mg	0,769	0,085	0,034	0,004	0,063	0,836	0,28	0,279
K	0,365	0,108	0,001	0,059	0,116	0,748	0,001	0,062
Na	0,026	0,396	0,01	0,028	0,001	0,009	0,001	0,001
Bs	0,312	0,004	0,02	0,027	0,029	0,66	0,371	0,074
CaCO3	0,792	0,26	0,921	0,064	0,001	0,081	0,063	0,287
FM	0,929	0,876	0,001	0,332	0,111	0,225	0,147	0,004
NH4	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,008	0,001
NO3	0,128	0,64	0,001	0,053	0,76	0,343	0,727	0,611
Pav	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,01	0,628	0,001	0,004	0,001
Fe	0,002	0,001	0,001	0,056	0,004	0,001	0,003	0,001
Cu	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,021	0,001	0,001	0,086	0,001
Zn	0,002	0,001	0,001	0,007	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001
Mn	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,058	0,002	0,012	0,001	0,001
Mo	0,006	0,001	0,006	0,001	0,016	0,012	0,004	0,001
Bba	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,044	0,149	0,002	0,002	0,03
AgSD_b	0,772	0,001	0,962	0,18	0,633	0,519	0,859	0,579
AgSD_c	0,236	0,121	0,567	0,489	0,003	0,014	0,488	0,001
AgSD_d	0,253	0,59	0,615	0,375	0,679	0,482	0,563	0,189
AgSD_e	0,049	0,001	0,282	0,941	0,005	0,022	0,413	0,001

Table 4.2. P-values of the listed parameters for case studies (CS) 10a till 15 analysed by the *envfit* program in R. P-values (p) less than or equal to 0.005 (in red) are considered statically significant. Explanantion of the physical and chemical properties applied can be found in the tabel in chapter Annexes.

In case-studies 6 and 7, the datapoints on the NMDS plots (Figure 4.3) are clearly grouped depending on the year of sampling. Also, different parameters significantly shaped the nematode communities grouped according to the sampling event. It is in both cases difficult to notice a clear influence of a certain parameter on the nematode communities found in a certain treatment. Especially in case-study 7 it can be noticed that the influence of a parameters in one group (direction) can be counteracted by a parameter in the other group (other direction) as the vectors are more or less pointed towards opposite directions.

For case-study 8, the situation is a little bit more interpretable since the datapoints are more grouped according to the treatment (Figure 4.3). At the start of the experiment (year 2020), none of the parameters influenced the nematode communities for any treatment as the vectors are not directed to the position of the data points. In 2023, at the end of the experiment, different parameters more or less influence the nematode communities isolated from different treatments. For example, the parameters OM and FM shaped the nematode communities of treatment "Ctrl", while for treatment "a", parameters Nt, Na and NH₄ played a significant role.

Case-studies 10a, 10b and 11, Continental region

In table 4.2, the p-values of the physical and chemical parameters measured for case-studies 10a, 10b and 11 indicate that respectively 9, 19 and 15 of those parameters significantly shape the nematode communities when considering the soil samples from the start, being it 2021 for CS10a and b and 2020 for CS11, and the end of the experiment (year 2023 for all 3 case-studies). Only the parameters POC, NH₄, Pav, Fe, Cu, Zn, Mn and Bba are directing the nematode communities in all 3 case-studies from the Continental region.

In case-study 10a, none of the parameters can be clearly linked to one of the agricultural activities conducted. All vectors are directed towards a position on the NMDS plot away from most data points (Figure 4.4). Although parameters were found to significantly shape nematode communities (Table 4.2), it is more likely depending on the year of sampling rather than the agricultural activities. The same conclusions can be made for case-study 10b although with some good-will parameters Cu and Mo shaped the nematode communities of treatment "Ctrl" and Bba the treatment "a" (3 repeats out of 4) in the year 2021 (Figure 4.4). For case-study 11 problems occurred to draw the NMDS plot. Any conclusions concerning the effect of parameters in shaping the nematode communities linked to any agricultural activity is as good as impossible.

Figure 4.4. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 10a, 10b and 11. The vectors are limited to those physical and chemical parameters that significantly shaped the nematode communities (see Table 4.2). Case-study 10a: a = use of additive + plant biostimulant + reduction of fungicides, b = use of additive + plant biostimulant + plant adjuvant + reduction of fungicides, Ctrl = control treatment = reduction of fungicides. Case-study 10b: a = cultivation with strip undersowing, b = cultivation with broad undersowing, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 11: a = extensive wheat farming, b = diversified extensive wheat farming, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional wheat farming. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments, a different symbol is used for the sampling events.

Case-study 12, Nemoral region

For case-study 12, only 3 out of 31 physical and chemical parameters (Mg, NH₄ and Mo) are shaping the nematode communities significantly (Table 4.2). The NMDS-plot (Figure 4.5) indicates that potentially the parameter NH₄ influenced the nematode community composition in the year 2023, so towards the end of the experiment. The other two parameters cannot be unambiguously linked to any treatment. However, Mo seemingly opposed NH₄ in shaping the nematode communities as their vectors are pointed toward opposite directions.

Figure 4.5. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-study 12: a = reduced tillage, b = no tillage, c = organic farming with conventional tillage, d = conventional farming with conventional tillage, e = control. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments, a different symbol is used for the sampling events. The vectors are limited to those physical and chemical parameters that significantly shaped the nematode communities (see Table 4.2).

Case-studies 13, 14a, 14b and 15, Boreal region

For case-studies 13, 14a, 14b and 15, p-values of respectively 33, 36, 37 and 36 physical and chemical parameters are listed in Table 4.2. Most parameters did not significantly shape the nematode community compositions. Only 12, 10, 11 and 12 parameters measured did significantly shape the nematode communities respectively. Two parameters, Fe and Zn, are shaping the nematode communities in all case-studies of the Boreal region (Table 4.2).

In figure 4.6, the NMDS plot shows that the parameters pHKCl and Zn especially shape the nematode communities of all treatments in the year 2020, while for the year 2022 NH₄ seems to be most important. These parameters seem to counteract each other as their vectors point into opposite directions. For case-study 14a there is not clear link between the significant parameters and the agricultural management. Only Fe, POC, Cu, Zn and pHKCl seem to have influenced both treatments in 2020, but they did not repeat this obviously in 2022. The same is the situation for case-study 14b. There is no obvious link between the parameters retained and the treatments. At some extend, Bba seem to have shaped treatment "a" in 2021, while in 2023 Mo, Fe, Pav and pH are the parameters to take into account. Finally concerning case-study 15, like in the other case-studies of this region, the datapoints are grouped according to the year of sampling and different parameters effect more or less obviously the treatments. Although it is difficult to see clear patterns.

Figure 4.6. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the first and last year of each treatment within case-studies 13, 14a, 14b and 15. The vectors are limited to those physical and chemical parameters that significantly shaped the nematode communities (see Table 4.2). Case-study 13: a = composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fibre" amendment after the early potato harvest, b = wood fibre sludge (zero fibre) amendment after the early potato harvest, Ctrl = control treatment = no amendments after the early potato harvest. Case-study 14a: a = organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat, Ctrl = control treatment = organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat. Case-study 14b: a = organic farming with autumn ploughing in winter wheat, Ctrl = control treatment = organic farming with autumn minimum tillage in winter wheat. Case-study 15: a = phacelia as catch-crop after the early potato harvest, b = rye as a catch crop after the early potato harvest, Ctrl = control treatment = no catch crop after the early potato harvest. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments, a different symbol is used for the sampling events.

4.3.2 Interrelationship between nematode communities and yield

Only in case-study 2 (p-value = 0,006), the yield is significantly shaping the nematode communities when considering results with p-values less or equal to 0.05. In all other case-studies the p-value was higher than 0.05 or could not be calculated due to insufficient data. The latter occurred for case-studies 10b, 11, 14a, 14b and 15. The NMDS plots for which the data was sufficient can be found in figures 4.7 till 4.12. The NMDS plots show that the datapoints are not on or closely positioned to the vector representing yield. With other words, the vector arrow is not pointing to any of the treatments

conducted in the case-studies, demonstrating that the yield is not shaping the nematode communities or vice versa, the nematode communities did not influence the yield. Only, as mentioned, in case-study 2 we see a rather small relationship with the treatment “c”. Also in case-study 8, although statistically not significant, we notice a certain, but rather clear, relationship with treatment “a”, while in case-study 9 the same can be concluded, however less obvious, for treatment “a” and “c”.

Case-studies 1 & 2, Mediterranean South region

Figure 4.7. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the last year of each treatment within case-studies 1 and 2. The vector is from the results concerning yield. Case-study 1: a = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced chemical fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced chemical fertilizer, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% chemical fertilizer. Case-study 2: a = reduced organic fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria and fungi, b = reduced organic fertilizer + biofertilizer bacteria, c = reduced organic, Ctrl = control treatment = 100% organic fertilizer. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments.

Case-studies 3, 4 & 5, Lusitanian region

Figure 4.8. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the last year of each treatment within case-studies 3, 4 and 5. The vector is from the results concerning yield. Case-study 3: a = alternative crop rotation 1, b = alternative crop rotation 2, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional crop rotation. Case-study 4: a = mycorrhiza + reduced P fertilization, b = mycorrhiza and no P fertilization, c = reduced P fertilization, d = no P fertilization, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional P fertilization. Case-study 5: a = conventional fungicide application, b = no fungicide application, Ctrl = control treatment = pest alert system. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments.

Case-studies 6 till 9, Atlantic Central region

Figure 4.9. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the last year of each treatment within case-studies 6 till 9. The vector is from the results concerning yield. Case-study 6: a = cover crop mowed and removed, b = plus farm yard manure, c = cover crop mowed and removed plus farm yard manure, d = plus farm yard manure co-composted with straw, e = cover crop mowed and removed plus farm yard manure co-composted with straw, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 7: a = Phacelia/Egyptian clover cover crop mixture, b = 5-species cover crop mixture, c = 12-species cover crop mixture, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 8: a = conventional extensive farming system, b = organic intensive farming system, c = organic extensive farming system, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional intensive farming system. Case-study 9: a = compost, b = farm yard manure, c = silage grass, Ctrl = control treatment = no fertilizer. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments.

Case-studies 10a, 10b and 11, Continental region

Figure 4.10. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the last year of each treatment within case-studies 10a, 10b and 11. The vector is from the results concerning yield. Case-study 10a: a = use of additive + plant biostimulant + reduction of fungicides, b = use of additive + plant biostimulant + plant adjuvant + reduction of fungicides, Ctrl = control treatment = reduction of fungicides. Case-study 10b: a = cultivation with strip undersowing, b = cultivation with broad undersowing, Ctrl = control treatment = business-as-usual. Case-study 11: a = extensive wheat farming, b = diversified extensive wheat farming, Ctrl = control treatment = conventional wheat farming. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments. Insufficient data in CS10b and 11 made it impossible to draw the NMDS plot.

Case-study 12, Nemoral region

Figure 4.11. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the last year of each treatment within case-study 12: a = reduced tillage, b = no tillage, c = organic farming with conventional tillage, d = conventional farming with conventional tillage, e = control. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments, a different symbol is used for the sampling events. The vector is from the results concerning yield.

Case-studies 13, 14a, 14b and 15, Boreal region

Figure 4.12. NMDS plot based on the number of ASV's of nematode communities from the last year of each treatment within case-studies 13, 14a, 14b and 15. The vector is from the results concerning yield. Case-study 13: a = composted pulp mill sludge "nutrient fibre" amendment after the early potato harvest, b = wood fibre sludge (zero fibre) amendment after the early potato harvest, Ctrl = control treatment = no amendments after the early potato harvest. Case-study 14a: a = organic farming with ploughing in springtime in spring wheat, Ctrl = control treatment = organic farming with springtime reduced tillage in spring wheat. Case-study 14b: a = organic farming with autumn ploughing in winter wheat, Ctrl = control treatment = organic farming with autumn minimum tillage in winter wheat. Case-study 15: a = phacelia as catch crop after the early potato harvest, b = rye as a catch crop after the early potato harvest, Ctrl = control treatment = no catch crop after the early potato harvest. Different colours are used to indicate the different treatments. Insufficient data in CS14a, 14b and 15 made it impossible to draw the NMDS plot.

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5 Earthworms

5.1 Introduction

Earthworms belong to the main drivers of soil processes and significantly contribute to the provision of ecosystem services soils. In arable soils, earthworm communities are shaped by the frequency and intensity of management measures by farmers such as tillage (Briones & Schmidt, 2017; van Capelle et al., 2012), pesticides (Pelosi et al. 2013, 2024), fertilizers (Curry 2004), crop rotations (Torppa and Taylor 2022) and crop residue management (Melman et al. 20219). These management practices further affect chemical and physical soil properties which control the soil as a habitat for earthworms and control their food sources. Finally, soil biodiversity performance and soil property development end up in quality and quantity of yield.

An in-depth evaluation of the diversity aspects of the earthworm communities in each case study across the six pedoclimatic regions in Europe, which were considered in WP5, is presented in the D5.2 report. The present report focuses on the relation of earthworm community variables and soil chemical as well as physical parameters and yield. Results are presented separately for each case study to provide detailed insights.

5.2 Material and Methods

Earthworm sampling and identification were done according to the methods, which are given in the previously published D5.1 report (Soto Gomez et al. 2020). Chapter 2.3 describes the sampling procedure in the field including the needed equipment. Chapter 5.1 explains the handling of the collected individuals in the lab. Furthermore, all information about species identification and their assignment to ecological groups is given.

Partial least squares (PLS) regression was used to interpret the relationships between earthworm-related variables (total density and mass, richness, densities of ecological groups) and different environmental variables (soil properties, gaseous emissions and crop yield). Of soil properties, a subset of the variables listed in Annexes Table 1.1 was used: of chemical soil properties pH, CEC, TOC, Pav, Nt, NH₄ and NO₂ were included; of physical soil properties BD, FMa and Agsd_b – Agsd_e were included.

PLS is a multivariate modeling approach that creates a number of latent orthogonal factors to explain the maximum variation in predictor and response matrices. It is particularly suitable when the explanatory variables are few and collinear (Wold et al. 2001). Due to the small data sets of each of the four experimental designs, cross-validation methods were not utilized. All analyses were conducted using the PLS procedure with the NIPALS algorithm in SAS.

To account for random and fixed environmental variation, year and treatment were included as categorical variables in all models but were omitted when their effects were minor. Earthworm variables were included as appropriate, e.g. excluding richness from the analyses when only one

species was present in the experiment. Three factors were chosen for each model, and variable importance values (VIP), predictor loading profiles and correlation loading plots were used for interpretation.

5.3 Results and discussion

Results for earthworms were obtained for CS3-CS5 (Lusitanian), CS6-CS9 (Atlantic), CS10-CS11 (Continental), CS12 (Nemoral) and CS13-CS15 (Boreal). Generally, the years were the predictors, which loaded strongly on the first and/or second factor in all CS3-CS15.

In the **Mediterranean** region, the environmental conditions were such adverse (dried-up soils due to lack of rain) that no earthworms were found in CS1 and CS2.

In **Lusitanian** fields, the first factor explained 21% of the variation in CS3, 40% in CS4 and 32% in CS5 (Table 5.1). The addition of more factors decreased R^2 .

Table 5.1. Cumulative variation (%) in predictors (X; soil, emission and yield variables) and responses (Y; earthworm variables) explained by each PLS factor for the three Lusitanian experimental fields.

N of factors	CS 3		CS 4		CS 5	
	R ² of X	R ² of Y	R ² of X	R ² of Y	R ² of X	R ² of Y
1	26.7	21.1	45.1	39.9	41.2	32.1
2	18.6	8.5	15.7	7.5	22.3	6.4
3	20.5	3.9	12.7	3.8	10.1	4.2

The earthworm variables were quite closely associated, especially in CS3 and CS5 (Figures 5.1 and 5.2). In CS3, the years 2021 and 2022 were the only predictors, which loaded strongly on the first and second factor but in opposite directions with the year 2022 strongly positive on the first and negative on the second factor (Figure 5.1). Both years loaded also strongly in CS4 (positive in 2022, negative in 2021) but on the first factor only. Roughly the same applied to CS5 (Figure 5.2). With respect to other predictors in CS4, Yield, NH₄, NO₃ and Pav loaded negatively on the first factor and TOC and Agsd_e positively on the second factor (Figure 5.1). Richness as earthworm variable was best explained by the year 2022 on the first factor in CS4 (Figure 5.1). POC and NH₄ showed a negative correlation with the earthworm responses in CS3 and CS4 (Figure 5.1). Additionally in CS4, FMa, NO₃, Pav and yield showed negative correlation with earthworm responses (Figure 5.1). In CS5, NO₃ loaded positive on the first and second factor (Figure 5.2). Yield, NH₄ and POC loaded highly negative on the first factor and Pav on the second factor.

Figure 5.1. Partial least squares (PLS) correlation loading plots illustrating the relationships between earthworm-related variables (red) and environmental variables (blue) in Lusitanian field experiments CS3 (left) and CS4 (right). Each observation's X-scores are represented by numbers (green). The loadings reflect the extent of variation in each variable explained by the first two factors. This is shown both collectively by the distance of each point from the origin and individually by the projections of these points onto the horizontal and vertical axes. Variables next to each other correlated strongly. Abbreviations: Dens = earthworm total density; Mass = earthworm total mass; Rich = earthworm species richness; Ane = earthworm anecic ecological group; Endo = earthworm endogeic ecological group; Epi = earthworm epigeic ecological group; Y = year (e.g. Y 2020); Tr = Treatment (e.g. Tr Ctrl). Other abbreviations as in Annexes Table 1.1.

Figure 5.2. Partial least squares (PLS) correlation loading plots illustrating the relationships between earthworm-related variables (red) and environmental variables (blue) in the Lusitanian field experiment

CS5. For the interpretation of the graph, see the legend of Figure 5.1. For abbreviations, see the legend of Figure 5.1. and Annexes Table 1.1.

In **Atlantic** fields, the first factor explained 44% of the variation in CS6, 34% in CS7, 30% in CS8 and 18% in CS9 (Table 5.2). The addition of more factors decreased R^2 .

Table 5.2. Cumulative variation (%) in predictors (X; soil, emission and yield variables) and responses (Y; earthworm variables) explained by each PLS factor for the four Atlantic experimental fields.

N of factors	CS 6		CS 7		CS 8		CS 9	
	R^2 of X	R^2 of Y						
1	40.7	44.4	47.8	33.5	23.7	29.5	41.1	17.5
2	36.2	0.7	19.6	5.9	23.7	2.7	10.5	13.1
3	6.2	2.2	8.5	4.8	12.4	5.3	7.4	6.2

In CS6 and CS8, the earthworm variables were closely associated (Figures 5.3 and 5.4). The predictors years were strongly loaded in all CS6-CS9 on the first and/or second factor. The year 2023 was the only predictor, which loaded always positively on the first factor in each case study. Contrary, the year 2022 loaded negatively in CS6 and CS9 whereas the year 2021 loaded negatively in CS7 and CS8 (Figures 5.3 and 5.4). On the second factor, the year 2022 loaded negatively in CS7 and the year 2020 negatively in CS 6 and CS8. In CS6, Yield and FMA loaded positively and strongly on the first factor (Figure 5.3). Both predictors together with the year 2023 explained best the six earthworm variables in CS6. Here, Agsd_e loaded strongly positively and NO_3 as well as POC negatively on the second factor (Figure 5.3). In CS7, NH_4 , NO_3 , POC and Agsd_e were negatively correlated with the earthworm variables (Figure 5.3). Earthworm biomass was best explained by Agsd_c and the densities of the three ecological groups were best explained by Pav, Yield and CEC in CS7 (Figure 5.3). In CS8, TOC and Nt loaded positively and strongly on the first and second factor (Figure 5.4). NH_4 loaded negatively on the first but positively on the second factor. In CS9, NH_4 as well as Agsd_e loaded negatively and Agsd_c, Nt, pH and Yield positively on the first factor (Figure 5.4). The predictor Agsd_d loaded also positively and explained best the earthworm variables total density and density of the endogeics (Figure 5.4).

Figure 5.3. Partial least squares (PLS) correlation loading plots illustrating the relationships between earthworm-related variables (red) and environmental variables (blue) in the Atlantic field experiments CS6 (left) and CS7 (right). For the interpretation of the graph, see the legend of Figure 5.1. For abbreviations, see the legend of Figure 5.1. and Annexes Table 1.1.

Figure 5.4. Partial least squares (PLS) correlation loading plots illustrating the relationships between earthworm-related variables (red) and environmental variables (blue) in the Atlantic field experiments CS8 (left) and CS9 (right). For the interpretation of the graph, see the legend of Figure 5.1. For abbreviations, see the legend of Figure 5.1. and Annexes Table 1.1.

In **Continental** fields, the first factor explained 44% of the variation in CS10a, 35% in CS10b and 32% in CS11 (Table 5.3). The addition of more factors decreased R².

Table 5.3. Cumulative variation (%) in predictors (X; soil, emission and yield variables) and responses (Y; earthworm variables) explained by each PLS factor for the three Continental experimental fields.

N of factors	CS 10a		CS 10b		CS 11	
	R ² of X	R ² of Y	R ² of X	R ² of Y	R ² of X	R ² of Y
1	34.0	43.8	33.1	35.0	33.1	32.2
2	32.9	6.7	27.8	6.4	19.9	8.4
3	12.3	4.2	5.4	7.6	20.1	3.5

In CS10a and 10b, the earthworm variables were closely associated (Figure 5.5). On the first factor, the year 2023 was positively loaded and on the second factor, the year 2022 was negatively and the year 2021 positively loaded (Figure 5.5). In CS 11 on the first factor, the year 2020 was positively and the year 2022 negatively loaded, whereas on the second factor, the year 2023 was positively loaded and the year 2021 was negatively loaded (Figure 5.6). In CS10a, The earthworm variables species richness, total density and density of the endogeics were best explained by Agsd_b and biomass and density of anecics were explained by FMa and BD (Figure 5.5). All these earthworm variables were negatively correlated with Agsd_c and Agsd_d. The predictors POC, NO₃, Yield and NH₄ loaded negatively on the first and positively on the second factor in CS10a (Figure 5.5). In CS10b, the earthworm variables were closely associated with FMa (Figure 5.5). The predictors Yield and NO₃ were negatively loaded on the first factor and pH and Agsd_b on the second factor (Figure 5.5). In CS11, CEC and POC were closely associated with earthworm biomass, total density, density of endogeics and species richness (Figure 5.5). Pav, NH₄ and Nt were negatively and FMa positively loaded on the first factor.

Figure 5.5. Partial least squares (PLS) correlation loading plots illustrating the relationships between earthworm-related variables (red) and environmental variables (blue) in the Continental field experiments CS10a (left) and CS10b (right). For the interpretation of the graph, see the legend of Figure 5.1. For abbreviations, see the legend of Figure 5.1. and Annexes Table 1.1.

Figure 5.6. Partial least squares (PLS) correlation loading plots illustrating the relationships between earthworm-related variables (red) and environmental variables (blue) in the Continental field experiment CS11. For the interpretation of the graph, see the legend of Figure 5.1. For abbreviations, see the legend of Figure 5.1. and Annexes Table 1.1.

In the **Nemoral** region, the first factor explained only 10% of the variation in CS12 (Table 5.4). The addition of more factors slightly increased R^2 .

Table 5.4. Cumulative variation (%) in predictors (X; soil, emission and yield variables) and responses (Y; earthworm variables) explained by each PLS factor for the Nemoral experimental field.

N of factors	CS 12	
	R ² of X	R ² of Y
1	24.9	9.8
2	26.6	8.1
3	12.5	16.0

In CS12, none of the earthworm factors were associated and well explained (Figure 5.7). They all loaded below 25% on the first and second factor. On the first factor, the year 2020 loaded positively and the year 2022 negatively. The year 2021 loaded strongly and positively on the second factor. On the first factor, the predictors Nt, POC, CEC and FMa loaded positively and BD, Pav and NO₃ negatively

(Figure 5.7). On the second factor, Agsd_e and NH₄ loaded positively and Agsd_b, Agsd_c and pH negatively.

Figure 5.7. Partial least squares (PLS) correlation loading plots illustrating the relationships between earthworm-related variables (red) and environmental variables (blue) in the Nemoral field experiment CS12. For the interpretation of the graph, see the legend of Figure 5.1. For abbreviations, see the legend of Figure 5.1. and Annexes Table 1.1.

In **Boreal** field CS13, approximately 50% of the variation in responses can be explained by the predictors (Table 5.5) with three factors.

Table 5.5. Cumulative variation (%) in predictors (X; soil, emission and yield variables) and responses (Y; earthworm variables) explained by each PLS factor for the four Boreal experimental fields.

N of factors	CS 13		CS 15		CS 14a		CS 14b	
	R ² of X	R ² of Y	R ² of X	R ² of Y	R ² of X	R ² of Y	R ² of X	R ² of Y
1	29.2	23.0	18.0	22.1	27.9	65.0	28.5	38.8
2	41.8	43.9	43.8	27.3	64.1	73.8	52.6	55.1
3	52.4	50.8	64.1	28.3	73.3	77.1	66.0	65.1

The predictors TOC, Nt, and FMa loaded highly on the first factor, indicating their strong influence (Figure 5.8). In contrast, NH₄, Agsd_e, and treatment loaded significantly on the second factor. In Boreal field CS15 (Figure 5.8), the first factor similarly explained about 22% of the variation, but the addition of more factors did not improve much the R². TOC showed a strong negative correlation with the earthworm responses in CS 15, as did also CO₂ and Agsd_c. The year 2021, NH₄, and Agsd_e loaded positively on the first factor, indicating their strong association to responses. These three

variables also loaded strongly on the second factor, while Agsd_b, POC, and the year 2020 loaded in the opposite direction.

Figure 5.8. Partial least squares (PLS) correlation loading plots illustrating the relationships between earthworm-related variables (red) and environmental variables (blue) in the Boreal field experiments CS13 (left) and CS15 (right). For the interpretation of the graph, see the legend of Figure 5.1. For abbreviations, see the legend of Figure 5.1. and Annexes Table 1.1.

In Boreal experiments CS 14a and CS 14b, the earthworm variables were relatively closely associated, and their variation explained by the predictors was higher than in the case of the potato fields CS 13 and CS 15 (Table 5.5, Fig. 5.9). In field CS 14a, the predictors CEC, POC and CO₂ loaded strongly positively and predictors Pav and NH₄ negatively on the first factor, which explained two-thirds of the earthworm response variation (Fig. 5.9). In CS 14 b there were comparable loadings on the first factor, with CEC and POC loading positively and Pav and NH₄ negatively. In CS 14a the effect of treatment was minor and was omitted from the analyses, whereas in CS 14b, control and ploughing treatments were separated along the Factor 3 axis (Fig. 5.9). In both sites, the study year was highly influential and the PLS model separated the years with the year 2022 correlating negatively with earthworm variables. In CS 14b the density of anecic earthworms and earthworm species richness were most closely associated with the control treatment.

Figure 5.9. Partial least squares (PLS) correlation loading plots illustrating the relationships between earthworm-related variables (red) and environmental variables (blue) in the Boreal field experiments CS14a (left) and CS14b (right). For the interpretation of the graph, see the legend of Figure 5.1. For abbreviations, see the legend of Figure 5.1. and Annexes Table 1.1.

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6.1 ANNEXES-tab

TABLE 1.1

ABBREVIATION	MEASURED VARIABLE
STARCON	starch content
Yield	crop yield
FWEIG	tuber weight
FTDISTRIBUT	tuber size distribution
Grmoist	moisture content of grains
Grprot	protein content of grains
BD	Soil Bulk density 5-15 cm
SA	Sand content
SI	Silt content
CL	Clay content
CH4	methane emission
CO2	carbon dioxide
N2O	nitrous oxide
pH	soil pH in water
EC	Electrical conductivity
OM	Organic Matter
TOC	Total organic carbon
POC	Particulate organic carbon
Nt	Total nitrogen
CEC	Cation exchange capacity
Ca	Exchangeable calcium
Mg	Exchangeable magnesium
K	Exchangeable potassium
Na	Exchangeable sodium
Bs	Sum of bases
CaCO3	calcium carbonate
FM	Actual field moisture content
NH4	ammonium
NO3	nitrate
Pav	available phosphorus
Cu	available copper
Zn	available zinc
Fe	available iron
Mn	available manganese
Mo	available molybdenum
Agzd_b	Soil aggregates size distribution >2000
Agzd_c	Soil aggregates size distribution 250_2000
Agzd_d	Soil aggregates size distribution 53_250
Agzd_e	Soil aggregates size distribution < 53

Table 1.1. Measured crop and soil derived variables used in data analyses of the report.

6.2 ANNEXES-figures

Figure A1.1. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 1. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure A1.2. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 2. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure A1.3. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 3. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure A1.4. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 4. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure A1.5. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 5. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001.

Figure A1.6. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 6. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001.

Figure A1.7. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 7. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure A1.8. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 8. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure A1.9. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 9. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Figure A1.10. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 10a. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure A1.11. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 10b. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure A1.12. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 11. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure A1.13. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 12. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure A1.14. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 13. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001.

Figure A1.15. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 14a. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure A1.16. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 14b. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure A1.17. Spearman's rank correlations between environmental factors and top 40 most abundant genera of Case study 15. The strength of the correlations is indicated by color intensity and the asterisk indicates the significance level of the correlation * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001.